

**RELATIONSHIP OF PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS AND STUDENT
PERFORMANCE AS MEDIATED BY MATHEMATICS
MOTIVATION AMONG MATHEMATICS MAJOR
IN TEACHER EDUCATION PROGRAM**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 10

Pages: 13-41

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2938

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14717740

Manuscript Accepted: 12-27-2024

Relationship of Problem-Solving Skills and Student Performance as Mediated by Mathematics Motivation among Mathematics Major in Teacher Education Program

Charmine F. Hormillada,* Jobell B. Jajalla
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship of problem-solving skills and student performance as mediated by mathematics motivation among mathematics major teacher education program. The study was quantitative non-experimental research that utilized descriptive-correlational, and mediation analyses. Using stratified random sampling specifically proportional allocation for the sampling techniques and Slovin's formula with 0.05 margin of error for the sample size, a sample of 152 randomly selected mathematics education students answered the surveys on the three variables. Results showed that the level of problem-solving skills and student performance were at all high level, moreover, the level of mathematics motivation was also at a high level. Results also revealed that the relationship between problem-solving skills and student performance, between problem-solving skills and mathematics motivation, and between mathematics motivation and student performance among mathematics major in teacher education program were all significant. Moreover, the results show that mathematics motivation fully mediated the relationship between problem-solving skills and student performance. In conclusion, the students demonstrated exceptional problem-solving skills and achieved good academic performance. Additionally, they had a really strong motivation for mathematics. While the problem-solving skills, performance and motivation of the mathematics major students were strong, they still required development in the areas of creative thinking, strategic competency, and self-efficacy. Students concentrated on creating methodical ways, look for further practice, and used resources like textbooks, online tutorials, and tutoring to solve these inadequacies. Also, improvement required efficient study techniques and regular practice.

Keywords: *problem-solving skills, student performance, motivation BSED-mathematics, Philippines*

Introduction

Globally, mathematics was regarded as one of the most important subjects in the school curriculum. It was the foundation of scientific and technological knowledge that contributes significantly toward the socioeconomic development of a nation. However, despite the highly decorated and recognized importance of mathematics, poor performance of the students in Mathematics which was reflected in their low achievement remains to be an issue of great concern of schools, colleges, and universities in many countries across the globe (Chand et al., 2021).

In the case of Indonesia, the PISA report (2012) showed that the achievement scores of Indonesian students in mathematics are recorded very low and was ranked the 64th out of 65 countries (Ajisuksmo & Saputri, 2017).

In the case of Indonesia, the PISA report (2012) showed that the achievement scores of Indonesian students in mathematics are recorded very low and was ranked the 64th out of 65 countries (Ajisuksmo & Saputri, 2017).

This concern had been an experienced of the universities of Indonesia. It was reported that Indonesian students' performance in mathematics ranked exceptionally low, placing 64th out of 65 countries. This posed a significant challenge in the country's education system, emphasizing the necessity for reforms and enhancements in teaching methodologies, curriculum, and the overall learning environment to improve academic standards, particularly in mathematics and other core subjects (Ajisuksmo & Saputri, 2017).

In the Philippines setting, specifically in Cebu Technology University where they conducted their study. Even though they already provided with educational modules, where it made to assist learners in developing the mathematical and logical abilities necessary to comprehend important ideas, low student performance is still very visible and a major concern. The 2013 TIMSS study where the issue was highlighted, revealed that Filipino students did poorly in math when compared to students in neighboring Asian countries. Even with the well-organized curriculum, students still have trouble understanding basic mathematical ideas. This performance disparity is indicative of more serious problems with student involvement, resources, and teaching strategies (Guinocor et al., 2020).

Since the primary focused of this study was on identifying the mediating effect of Mathematics Motivation to the relationship between problem-solving skills and students' performance, this study was crucial for our society. If we understand this connection better, we can improve how we teach math, develop new curricula, and inspire future math educators. This, in turn, helps them excel in important areas and contribute meaningfully to the workforce, especially in solving real-world problems. Therefore, the urgency to handle this research is paramount, since it is imperative that these issues be resolve if mathematics instruction is to be improve and helps Filipino students succeed both nationally and internationally. Through strengthening teaching methods and providing better resources, we can provide them with the skills they need to compete on a global scale.

Numerous research studies had addressed students' performance in Mathematics but some key aspects remain unexplored. For instance,

a study of Zhang et al. (2021) investigated the relationship between mathematics motivation and performance in students from grades 9 to 12 but did not consider problem-solving skills as a variable. Additionally, this study did not pay attention to Bachelor of Science in Education (BSED) students majoring in mathematics, who played a crucial role in shaping future educators. The researchers examined the connection between mathematical problem-solving skills, self-regulated learning, homework behaviors, motivation, and metacognition. While problem-solving was part of this study, it did not specifically focus on its relevance to student performance and mathematical creativity. Lastly, a study by Hassan et al. (2017) explored problem-solving skills in conjunction with metacognitive awareness among secondary students, but it did not delve into the relationship between problem-solving skills and student performance as mediated by mathematics motivation, especially within mathematics major teacher education programs. This unique research contributed valuable insights and help fill gaps in the existing body of knowledge in this field.

This research study intended to disseminate the finding of my research study on relationship of problem-solving skills and student performance as mediated by mathematics motivation among mathematics major in teacher education program through hardbound copies distributed strategically within our academic community. I coordinated with the research office to arranged a formal presentation and distributed hardbound copies to faculty and staff during the event. Also, I ensured that hardbound copies were prominently available in the library, making them easily accessible to students and researchers.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship of problem-solving skills and student performance as mediated by mathematics motivation among mathematics major in teacher education program. As a result, the research aimed to accomplish the following goals:

1. To determine the level of problem-solving skills of the students in terms of:
 - 1.1. creative thinking;
 - 1.2. analysis;
 - 1.3. decision making;
 - 1.4. emotional intelligence;
 - 1.5. researching skills; and
 - 1.6. team working
2. To determine the level of student performance of the students in terms of:
 - 2.1. conceptual understanding;
 - 2.2. procedural fluency;
 - 2.3. strategic competence;
 - 2.4. adaptive reasoning; and
 - 2.5. productive disposition
3. To determine the level of mathematics motivation of the students in terms of:
 - 3.1. intrinsic goal orientation;
 - 3.2. extrinsic goal orientation;
 - 3.3. task value;
 - 3.4. control beliefs for learning;
 - 3.5. self-efficacy; and
 - 3.6. test anxiety.
4. To determine the significant relationships among:
 - 4.1. problem-solving skills and student performance;
 - 4.2. problem-solving skills and mathematics motivation; and
 - 4.3. student performance and mathematics motivation.
5. To determine the relationship of problem-solving skills and student performance as mediated by mathematics motivation.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used the quantitative non-experimental research design in descriptive type since the variables involved cannot be manipulated because they were naturally existing attribute (Pearson, 2010). Hence, controlling or manipulating them was unethical. Non experimental research involved variables that were not manipulated by the researcher. Instead, those were studied as they existed. One reason for using non-experimental research was that many variables of interest in social science cannot be manipulated because they were attribute variables, such as gender, socioeconomic status, learning style, or any other personal characteristic or trait (Belli, 2008).

In this study, non-experimental methods are suitable to examine the relationship between problem-solving skills, student performance, and mathematics motivation among mathematics major in teacher education program. Providing insights for educational strategies, the study can offer valuable insights into how individual differences and learning preferences affect mathematical performance, which can

inform educational strategies and curriculum development in teacher education program.

Correlational research was a type of research that examines the statistical relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. It was a non-experimental research design that seeks to establish the degree of association or correlation between two or more variables (Hassan, 2023). It was used to determine whether there was a correlation between the variables and, if so, what kind of correlation existed. Correlational research did not involve manipulating any independent variable but instead looks at existing patterns in the data. The main goal of correlational research was to identify relationships between variables and understand how they were related. This type of research was used to explore cause-and-effect relationships or observed data patterns (Pallister, 2023).

In this context, correlational research demonstrated the value of analyzing statistical relationships between factors such as problem-solving skills, student performance, and mathematics motivation for mathematics without modifying them in a controlled setting. This method, which is non-experimental in nature, recognizes the complexities of real-world educational environments and offers insights that are essential for customizing successful teaching tactics to enhance students' achievement in mathematics.

Mediation analysis, in its simplest form, represented the addition of a third variable to the $X \rightarrow Y$ relation, whereby X caused the mediator, M , and caused Y , so $X \rightarrow M \rightarrow Y$. This analytical approach provided a deeper understanding of the mechanisms through which the independent variable affected the dependent variable. By identifying and exploring the role of the mediator, researchers gained insights into the underlying processes and pathways that contributed to the observed relationship between X and Y . Mediation analysis was particularly valuable in uncovering the intervening variables that explained how and why changes in X led to changes in Y (MacKinnon et al., 2017).

In this context, the researcher looked at the complex relationships that exist between students' performance (Y), mathematics motivation (M), and problem-solving skills (X). According to my investigation, there is a link ($X \rightarrow M \rightarrow Y$) that shows how students' passion for mathematics mediates the impact of their problem-solving skills on their performance. These understandings are essential for developing curricula and teaching methods that are tailored to maximize mathematics learning within our unique educational environment.

The independent variable in this study was problem-solving skills while the dependent variable was students' performance of mathematics major students and the mediating variable was the mathematics motivation. In this study, the researcher determined the relationship between problem-solving skills and students' performance and the mediating effect of mathematics motivation on the relationship towards problem-solving skills and students' performance of mathematics major students.

Respondents

The target respondents of this study were students enrolled in Academic Year 2023-2024 of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. The respondents in the study were primarily drawn from this institution using the Slovin's formula with a margin of error of 0.05. A total of 152 students out of 245 students were the respondents of the study across all the year level in mathematics program. Moreover, to ensure an accurate distribution of samples, the researcher utilized stratified random sampling, specifically proportional allocation.

Stratified random sampling is a helpful technique. It entails segmenting the population according to significant traits into smaller groupings, or strata. The sample is guaranteed to include every group appropriately. Table 1 shows the distribution of the population of this study.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Schools</i>	<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage %</i>
Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd)- Mathematics	1st	119	74	30.13
Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd)- Mathematics	2nd	50	31	12.66
Bachelor of Elementary Education (BSEd)- Mathematics	3rd	43	27	10.89
Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd)- Mathematics	4th	33	20	8.36
Total		245	152	62.04

Instrument

The study adapted three questionnaires from web sources to measure the variables. To measure the mediating variable of this study which was mathematics motivation, the researcher utilized the instrument entitled, "The Survey Study of Mathematics Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MMSLQ)" from the study of Liu and Chun Hung (2010). Liu & Chun Hung used of content experts and the high response provides a high level of confidence in the content-validity of the instrument. Hence, MMSLQ was appropriate in this study. The adapted questionnaire consists of six type/set of test items with 5 number of items in each set/type. A Cronbach α analysis was calculated for each component of mathematics motivation scale. The Cronbach α analysis could examine if the items were internally consistent, stable, and homogenous. In order to raise the reliability and lower the error, some unsuitable items had been deleted. After the reliability analysis, item 8, item 18, item 30, and item 32 were deleted, and the value of Cronbach α raised to .884. After the reliability analysis, item 10, and item 21 were deleted, and the value of Cronbach α raised to .872. After the reliability analysis, item 12, was deleted, and the value of Cronbach α raised to .759.

The second set of instruments was adapted from the work of Dayaganon et al. (2022) which entitled “Perceived Level of Competence of the University Students’ Problem-Solving Skills in Mathematics in the New Normal” that measured the problem-solving skills of the students in terms of creative thinking, analysis, decision making, emotional intelligence, researching skills and team working. Each indicator had five questions and validated by the panel of experts with a Cronbach’s Alpha internal coefficient whose value was .85. It was indicated the sufficient evidence that favor validity and reliability test.

The third set of instruments was adapted from the study of Altarawneh and Marei (2021) entitled, “Mathematical Proficiency and Preservice Classroom Teachers’ Instructional Performance” that measured the students’ performance in terms of conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, strategic competence, adaptive reasoning and productive disposition. Each indicator had five questions and validated by the panel of experts. Reliability of the card was verified by calculating internal consistency coefficient using Cronbach Alpha whose value was (0.91), considered acceptable for the purpose of the study.

The Likert Scale was used as the basis in describing the level of the respondents’ mathematics motivations, problem-solving skills and student performance. Likert Scale requires individual to check on the box/blank in response to a large number of items concerning to an attitude, object, and stimulus.

Procedure

In gathering the data, the researcher underwent the following steps and procedure in gathering data for the study.

Seeking the Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher had the questionnaires validated by the internal validators. After the approval of the panel of experts, the researcher sent a permission letter to the school administrator to permit them to conduct the aforementioned study. The researcher asked permission from the College President of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology to conduct the study in all year level of mathematics program. After the approval of the administrator, the researcher started to formulate the instrument has been used in conducting the study.

Distribution and Retrieval of Questionnaire. Upon the approval of the college president, the researcher personally distributed the research instruments to the respondents and managed them to respond into it. After which, the researcher personally retrieved the research instruments.

Collection and Tabulation of Data. Lastly, after the retrieval, the data drawn from the instruments were tabulated. The statistical results had been analyzed and interpreted. From the data, conclusions were drawn and recommendations were formulated based on the findings of the study.

Data Analysis

The data gathered through the questionnaires were tallied and treated using the following statistical tools. The following statistical tools were used in the computation of data and to test the hypotheses at alpha 0.05 level of significance.

Mean. This was used to determine the level of problem-solving skills, students’ performance, and mathematics motivation.

Pearson r Correlation. This was used to determine the relationship between, problem-solving skills and their students’ performance, the relationship between problem-solving skills and mathematics motivation, and the connection between mathematics motivation and students’ performance which are the variables of this study.

Structural Equation Modeling Using Mediation Analysis. This was carried out to figure out whether the mediating variable had any impact on the relationship between an independent variable and a dependent variable using the indirect effect. It was utilized in this research to find out whether mathematics motivation played a mediating role on the relationship between problem-solving skills and their students’ performance as the mean statement of the problem.

Ethical Considerations

The participants of this study were mathematics major students of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. To ensure the sound conduct of the study, the researcher addressed ethical considerations accordingly.

Furthermore, the greatest ethical standards must be followed by researchers when they work with participants in their studies. Ensuring the study’s ethical validity is the primary objective of this quantitative research in order to safeguard the wellbeing of its participants. The researcher talked about how the study as a whole was able to adhere to Denzin and Lincoln’s (2011) recommendations, which focused on three important principles: informed consent, risk of harm, anonymity and secrecy, and conflict of interest.

Informed Consent. The word was made up of two key elements: ‘informed’ and ‘consent,’ both of which requires careful study. Participants was thoroughly informed about what was required to them, how the data was used, and the potential consequences (if any). Participants gave explicit, active, signed agreement to participate in the study, which includes recognizing their rights to view their data and the ability to withdraw at any time. The process of informed consent was thought of as a contract between the researcher and the participants (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In this study, the researcher added an informed consent question in a google form, and also asking the respondents of the study if they

were willing to answer the survey questionnaire despite the risk. If the respondents had doubts about the survey questionnaire, they politely decline. But for those respondents who voluntarily participating, they were strongly encouraged. The researcher ensured that all the respondents were enthusiastic about it and eager to answer and participate.

Risk of Harm, Anonymity and Confidentiality. Participants' identities were kept private or anonymous, and assurances were go beyond preserving their names to include avoiding the use of self-identifying comments and information. A key step in protecting participants from potential damage is anonymity and confidentiality (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In the context of this study, to protect the respondents, their identities are being kept in private and not linked to their personal details. For example, the researcher not just hiding their names but also avoiding any comments that might reveal who they are. Ensuring anonymity helps prevent negative effects or harm that might come from their information being disclosed. Keeping details confidential is crucial for maintaining their privacy and safety.

Moreover, we also considered the Republic Act No. 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, safeguards individual personal information and communication systems, both in government and private sectors. Section 2, under it is general provisions, asserts the state's policy to uphold the fundamental human right to the privacy of communication while facilitating the free flow of the information to foster innovation and development.

Conflict of Interest. Existing relationships or previous activities by the researcher could possibly cause a conflict of interest, which must be disclosed in a transparent manner in an ethics approval application so that the committee could provide advice on how to handle the conflict (Lune & Berg, 2017).

In this context, the researcher stated that there were no commercial or financial ties involved in the research. This means that the study was done without any outside business influences. There were no financial relationships that could have affected the results. The researcher wanted to ensure the study was unbiased and free from any conflicts of interest. This adds credibility to the research.

Results and Discussion

Presented in the section below were the discussions of the data on the relationship of problem-solving skills and student performance as mediated by mathematics motivation among math major in teacher education program. This chapter presented the data result on the level of problem solving skills in terms of creative thinking, analysis, decision making, emotional intelligence, researching skills and team working; the level of student performance in terms of conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, strategic competence, adaptive reasoning and productive disposition; and the level of mathematical motivation in terms of intrinsic goal orientation, extrinsic goal orientation, task value, control beliefs for learning, self-efficacy and test anxiety. This also include the significant relationship among problem solving skills and student performance, significant relationship among problem solving skills and mathematical motivation, significant relationship among student performance and mathematical motivation and the relationship of problem-solving skills and student performance as mediated by mathematical motivation. Analysis and interpretation of the data, which were also done in parallel with the research objectives.

Level of Problem-Solving Skills of the Students in Terms of Creative thinking

The level of problem-solving skills was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, creative thinking. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 2 was the level of problem-solving skills in terms of critical thinking. The data revealed that the level of teaching quality in terms of classroom climate had a total mean of 3.99 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of creative thinking is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Table 2. Level of Problem-Solving Skills in terms of Creative thinking

<i>Creative Thinking</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Making charts and tables to help me in finding answers on problems.	3.99	High
2. Creating my own formula on the given mathematical problem.	3.68	High
3. Trying to find another efficient way to solve the problem when I hear some ideas and solutions.	4.15	High
4. Developing an implementation plan to solve a problem.	4.04	High
5. Making an illustration related to the problem.	4.11	High
Overall	3.99	High

The highest mean was 4.15 which means high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by the first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 3 - Trying to find another efficient way to solve the problem when I hear some ideas and solutions.

In contrast, the lowest mean was 3.68 but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 2 - Creating my own formula on the given mathematical problem.

Level of Problem-Solving Skills in terms of Analysis

The level of problem-solving skills was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, analysis. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 3 was the level of problem-solving skills in terms of analysis. The data revealed that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of analysis had a total mean of 4.31 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicated that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of analysis is always observed by the first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

The highest mean was 4.51 which means very high. This means that the item is always observed by the first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This is from item no. 1 – Checking my calculations by calculating again. In contrast, the lowest mean was 4.25 but with a descriptive equivalent of high.

Table 3. Level of Problem-Solving Skills in terms of Analysis

<i>Analysis</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Checking my calculations by calculating again.	4.51	Very High
2. Recognizing and clarifying the confused points after class.	4.26	Very High
3. Selecting relevant steps to solve the problem.	4.29	Very High
4. Evaluating potential solutions carefully and thoroughly against a predefined standard.	4.26	Very High
5. Evaluating solutions, and take time to think about how I should between options.	4.25	High
Overall	4.31	Very High

This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 5 - Evaluating solutions and take time to think about how I should between options.

In contrast, the lowest mean was 4.25 but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 5 - Evaluating solutions and take time to think about how I should between options.

Level of Problem-Solving Skills in Terms of Decision Making

The level of problem-solving skills was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, decision making. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 4 was the level of problem-solving skills in terms of decision making. The data revealed that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of decision making had a total mean of 4.20 with a descriptive equivalent of high.

This indicated that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of decision making was oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

The highest mean was 4.26 which means very high. This means that the item is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 2 - Making final decision in the end of my problem-solving process.

Table 4. Level of Problem-Solving Skills in terms of Decision Making

<i>Decision Making</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Clarifying the information in Mathematics that I heard and assessing it if it is persuasive.	4.20	High
2. Making final decision in the end of my problem-solving process.	4.26	Very High
3. Modifying whether my decisions are working promptly modify them as needed.	4.13	High
4. Selecting relevant materials to solve the problem.	4.18	High
5. Taking time to decide and design an action plan before actually calculating.	4.22	High
Overall	4.20	High

In contrast, the lowest mean was 4.13 but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 3 - Modifying whether my decisions are working promptly modify them as needed.

Level of Problem-Solving Skills in Terms of Emotional Intelligence

The level of problem-solving skills was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, emotional intelligence. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 5 is the level of problem-solving skills in terms of emotional intelligence. The data revealed that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of emotional intelligence had a total mean of 4.06 with a descriptive equivalent of high.

This indicated that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of emotional intelligence is oftentimes observed by mathematics major students.

Table 5. *Level of Problem-Solving Skills in terms of Emotional Intelligence*

<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Maintaining emotional balance even when I got low scores on quizzes and activities.	4.14	High
2. Reflecting on the answer only if all is checked giving a clear, exact and precise answer.	4.14	High
3. Making sure that my problems will not upset me even how difficult they are.	4.12	High
4. Feeling confident with my answers because I have solutions to the any math problems.	3.89	High
5. Following my instinct that my answers are correct when answering a problem in mathematics.	4.02	High
Overall	4.06	High

The highest mean was 4.14 which means high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from items no. 1 – maintaining emotional balance even when I got low scores on quizzes and activities, and item No. 2 - reflecting on the answer only if all is checked giving clear, exact and precise answer. In contrast, the lowest mean was 3.89 but with a descriptive equivalent of high.

This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 4 – feeling confident with my answers because I have solutions to the any math problem.

Level of Problem-Solving Skills in Terms of Researching Skills

The level of problem-solving skills was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, researching skills. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 6 was the level of problem-solving skills in terms of researching skills. The data revealed that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of researching skills had a total mean of 4.25 with a descriptive equivalent of high.

Table 6. *Level of Problem-Solving Skills in terms of Researching Skills*

<i>Researching Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Trying to find out another efficient way to solve the problem from books and internet sources.	4.31	Very High
2. Selecting relevant materials to solve the problem.	4.28	Very High
3. Looking for other solution to the problem to have options.	4.24	High
4. Acquiring knowledge through online research courses.	4.22	High
5. Consulting more experienced colleagues in mathematics.	4.18	High
Overall	4.25	High

This indicated that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of researching skills is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

The highest mean was 4.28 which means very high. This means that the item is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 2 – selecting relevant materials to solve the problem.

In contrast, the lowest mean was 4.18 but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 5 – consulting more experienced colleagues in Mathematics.

Level of Problem-Solving Skills in Terms of Team Working

The level of problem-solving skills was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, team working. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 7 was the level of problem-solving skills in terms of team working. The data revealed that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of team working had a total mean of 4.29 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicated that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of team working is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Table 7. *Level of Problem-Solving Skills in terms of Team Working*

<i>Team Working</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Showing excellence in teamwork that will maximize results.	4.29	Very High
2. Participating with my team's gathering of information through brainstorming.	4.29	Very High
3. Ensuring that team-related works handled and completed.	4.29	Very High
4. Engaging and displaying positive attitude in math-related group activities.	4.31	Very High
5. Providing workable solutions to problems that the team encountered.	4.30	Very High
Overall	4.29	Very High

The highest mean was 4.31 which means very high. This means that the item is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 4 – engaging and displaying positive attitude in math-related group activities.

In contrast, the lowest mean was 4.29 but with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 1 - showing excellence in team work that will maximize results, item no. 2 - participating with my team's gathering of information through brainstorming, and item no. 3 - Ensuring that team-related works handled and completed.

Summary on the Level of Problem-Solving Skills of the Students

Presented in Table 8 was the overall level of problem-solving skills in terms of creative thinking, analysis, decision making, emotional intelligence, researching skills and team working. The data revealed that the level of problem-solving skills of mathematics major students has a total mean of 4.18 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of problem-solving skills is oftentimes manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Further, the highest mean was 4.31 with the descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicated that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of analysis is always manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Table 8. *Summary on the Level of Problem-Solving Skills*

<i>Problem-Solving Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Creative Thinking	3.99	High
Analysis	4.31	Very High
Decision Making	4.20	High
Emotional Intelligence	4.06	High
Researching Skills	4.25	High
Team Working	4.29	Very High
Overall	4.18	High

In contrast, the lowest indicator was creative thinking which obtained a mean of 3.99 with a descriptive equivalent of high. Followed by the indicator emotional intelligence which obtained a mean of 4.06 with a descriptive equivalent of high. These indicated that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of creative thinking and emotional intelligence is oftentimes manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Also, decision making obtained a mean of 4.20 which means high. This indicated that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of decision making is oftentimes manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Moreover, teamworking obtained a mean of 4.29 which means very high. This indicated that the level of problem-solving in terms of team working is always manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Lastly, researching skills obtained a mean of 4.25 which means high. This indicated that the level of problem-solving skills in terms of researching skills is oftentimes manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Level of Student Performance in Terms of Conceptual Understanding

The level of student performance was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, conceptual understanding. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 9. *Level of Student Performance in terms of Conceptual Understanding*

<i>Conceptual Understanding</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Highlighting the importance of the mathematical concept and how to use it correctly.	4.38	Very High
2. Presenting and modelling math concepts to develop conceptual comprehension.	4.14	High
3. Interpreting basic mathematics.	4.20	High
4. Defining the concept in a correct mathematical language.	4.17	High
5. Relating new conceptual knowledge to the old one in a meaningful manner.	4.18	High
Overall	4.21	High

Presented in Table 9 was the level of student performance in terms of conceptual understanding. The data revealed that the level of student performance in terms of conceptual understanding had a total mean of 4.21 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of student performance in terms of conceptual understanding is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

The highest mean was 4.38 which means very high. This means that the item is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 1 – highlighting the importance of the mathematical concept and how to use it correctly.

In contrast, the lowest mean was 4.14 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from items no. 2 – presenting and modelling math concepts to develop conceptual comprehension.

Level of Student Performance in Terms of Procedural Fluency

The level of student performance was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, procedural fluency. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 10. *Level of Student Performance in terms of Procedural Fluency*

<i>Procedural Fluency</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Doing mental calculation for accurate problem solution.	4.09	High
2. Using problem-solving method.	4.22	High
3. Verifying the correct answer.	4.44	Very High
4. Explaining concept interrelations in connection with solution.	4.14	High
5. Using methods to explore presented mathematical ideas.	4.24	High
Overall	4.22	High

Presented in Table 10 was the level of student performance in terms of procedural fluency. The data revealed that the level of student performance in terms of procedural fluency had a total mean of 4.22 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of student performance in terms of procedural fluency is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

The highest mean was 4.44 which means very high. This means that the item is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 3 – verifying the correct answer. In contrast, the lowest mean was 4.09 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from items no. 1 – doing mental calculation for accurate problem solution.

Level of Student Performance in Terms of Strategic Competence

The level of student performance was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, strategic competence. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 11 was the level of student performance in terms of strategic competence. The data revealed that the level of student performance in terms of strategic competence had a total mean of 4.17 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of student performance in terms of strategic competence is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Table 11. *Level of Student Performance Skills in terms of Strategic Competence*

<i>Strategic Competence</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Presenting mathematical problems in several ways.	4.17	High
2. Crafting hypotheses that are required in any math problem.	4.04	High
3. Creating problems that mathematically solvable.	4.18	High
4. Using method in determining necessary suitable strategies to effectively solve problems.	4.26	Very High
5. Relating math problems to real life for easy understanding.	4.18	High
Overall	4.17	High

The highest mean was 4.26 which means very high. This means that the item is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 4 – using method in determining necessary suitable strategies to effectively solve problems.

In contrast, the lowest mean was 4.04 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from items no. 2 – crafting hypotheses that are required in any math problem.

Level of Student Performance in Terms of Adaptive Reasoning

The level of student performance was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, adaptive reasoning. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 12. *Level of Student Performance in terms of Adaptive Reasoning*

<i>Adaptive Reasoning</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Justifying the solution method by analyzing its step-by-step rationale.	4.26	Very High
2. Presenting open ended life problems that can be solved through different ways.	4.07	High
3. Checking errors and finding ways to correct them.	4.28	Very High
4. Articulating my thoughts clearly to uncover the reasons behind the errors.	4.22	High
5. Providing some expectations and guessing for problem solution.	4.14	High
Overall	4.19	High

Presented in Table 12 was the level of student performance in terms of adaptive reasoning. The data revealed that the level of student performance in terms of strategic competence had a total mean of 4.19 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the

level of student performance in terms of adaptive reasoning is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

The highest mean was 4.28 which means very high. This means that the item is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 3 – checking errors and finding ways to correct them.

In contrast, the lowest mean was 4.07 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from items no. 2 – presenting open ended life problems that can be solved through different ways.

Level of Student Performance in Terms of Productive Disposition

The level of student performance was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, productive disposition. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 13 is the level of student performance in terms of productive disposition. The data revealed that the level of student performance in terms of productive disposition had a total mean of 4.21 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of student performance in terms of adaptive reasoning is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

The highest mean was 4.36 which means very high. This means that the item is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 1 – recognizing my efforts to boost motivation and morale.

Table 13. *Level of Student Performance in terms of Productive Disposition*

<i>Productive Disposition</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Recognizing my efforts to boost motivation and morale.	4.36	Very High
2. Securing a safe ambience to encourage me to work anxiety free.	4.19	High
3. Highlighting and appreciating role of math in my life.	4.19	High
4. Utilizing technology to simplify mathematical information.	4.20	High
5. Establishing correlations between mathematics and other branches of science.	4.12	High
Overall	4.21	High

In contrast, the lowest mean was 4.12 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from items no. 5 – establishing correlation between mathematics and other branches of science

Summary on the Level of Student Performance of the Students

Presented in Table 14 was the overall level of student performance in terms of conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, strategic competence, adaptive reasoning and productive disposition. The data revealed that the level of student performance of mathematics major students has a total mean of 4.20 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of student performance is oftentimes manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Further, the highest mean was 4.22 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of student performance in terms of procedural fluency is oftentimes manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

In contrast, the lowest indicator was creative thinking which obtained a mean of 4.17 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of student performance in terms of strategic competence is oftentimes manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Moreover, adaptive reasoning obtained a mean of 4.19 which means high. This indicated that the level of student performance in terms of adaptive reasoning is oftentimes manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Table 14. *Summary on the Level of Student Performance*

<i>Student Performance</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Conceptual Understanding	4.21	High
Procedural Fluency	4.22	High
Strategic Competence	4.17	High
Adaptive Reasoning	4.19	High
Productive Disposition	4.21	High
Overall	4.20	High

Lastly, conceptual understanding and productive disposition obtained a mean 4.21 which means high. This indicated that the level of student performance in terms of conceptual understanding and productive disposition is oftentimes manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Level of Mathematics Motivation in Terms of Intrinsic Goal Orientation

The level of mathematics motivation was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, intrinsic goal orientation. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 15 was the level of mathematics motivation in terms of intrinsic goal orientation. The data revealed that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of intrinsic goal orientation had a total mean of 4.20 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of intrinsic goal orientation is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

The highest mean was 4.29 which means very high. This means that the item is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 5 – learning math to improve my logical thinking.

Table 15. *Level of Mathematics Motivation in terms of Intrinsic Goal Orientation*

<i>Intrinsic Goal Orientation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Aiming for challenging materials in math class because they helped me learn more.	4.18	High
2. Enjoying challenging math materials despite its difficulty because it fuels my curiosity.	4.20	High
3. Hoping to understand the content of the learning material used in the math class.	4.27	Very High
4. Wanting more projects and homework to learn, regardless of whether they boost my scores or not.	4.05	High
5. Learning math to improve my logical thinking.	4.29	Very High
Overall	4.20	High

In contrast, the lowest mean was 4.05 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 4 – wanting more projects and homework to learn, regardless of whether they boost my scores or not.

Level of Mathematics Motivation in Terms of Extrinsic Goal Orientation

The level of mathematics motivation was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, extrinsic goal orientation. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 16 was the level of mathematics motivation in terms of extrinsic goal orientation. The data revealed that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of extrinsic goal orientation had a total mean of 4.15 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of extrinsic goal orientation is oftentimes observed by the first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

The highest mean was 4.32 which means very high. This means that the item is always observed by the involved respondents. This was from item no. 1 – aiming to get best grades in math class.

Table 16. *Level of Mathematics Motivation in terms of Extrinsic Goal Orientation*

<i>Extrinsic Goal Orientation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Aiming to get best grades in math class.	4.32	Very High
2. Taking math class to improve my overall academic score.	4.26	Very High
3. Wanting to get higher scores in math class because I want to show my capability to my classmates.	4.11	High
4. Hoping to attend an ideal university via learning math.	4.07	High
5. Targeting higher scores in math class to gain recognition from others.	3.99	High
Overall	4.15	High

In contrast, the lowest mean was 3.99 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by the first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from the item no. 5 – targeting higher scores in math to gain recognition from others.

Level of Mathematics Motivation in Terms of Task Value

The level of mathematics motivation was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, task value. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 17 was the level of mathematics motivation in terms of task value. The data revealed that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of task value had a total mean of 4.22 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of task value is oftentimes observed by the first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

The highest mean was 4.24 which means high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 5 – discovering that what I learn in the math class is applicable in my daily life.

In contrast, the lowest mean was 4.20 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first

year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from items no. 4 – enjoying every topic and content in math class.

Table 17. *Level of Mathematics Motivation in terms of Task Value*

<i>Task Value</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Applying the skills, I learned from math class in other class.	4.21	High
2. Finding interest in learning the materials used in math class to be useful.	4.21	High
3. Finding the learning materials used in math class to be useful.	4.22	High
4. Enjoying every topic and content in math class.	4.20	High
5. Discovering that what I learn in the math class is applicable in my daily life.	4.24	High
Overall	4.15	High

Level of Mathematics Motivation in Terms of Control Beliefs for Learning

The level of mathematics motivation was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, control beliefs for learning. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 18 was the level of mathematics motivation in terms of control beliefs for learning. The data revealed that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of control beliefs for learning had a total mean of 4.34 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicated that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of control beliefs for learning is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

The highest mean was 4.39 which means very high. This means that the item is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 2 – assuming that if I study hard, I can understand the content of the learning materials in math.

In contrast, the lowest mean was 4.29 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the item is always observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from items no. 3 – acknowledging that if I struggle to understand math topic, that is because I don't study hard.

Table 18. *Level of Student Performance in terms of Control Beliefs for Learning*

<i>Control Beliefs for Learning</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Thinking that if I have the correct learning pattern for studying math, I can learn better.	4.36	Very High
2. Assuming that if I study hard, I can understand the content of the learning materials in math.	4.39	Very High
3. Acknowledging that if I struggle to understand math topic, that is because I don't study hard.	4.29	Very High
4. Believing that paying full attention in math class will give me better grades.	4.32	Very High
5. Believing that having enough time to practice in math would lead to better performance.	4.32	Very High
Overall	4.34	Very High

Level of Mathematics Motivation in Terms of Self-Efficacy

The level of mathematics motivation was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, self-efficacy. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 19 was the level of mathematics motivation in terms of self-efficacy. The data revealed that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of self-efficacy had a total mean of 3.95 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of self-efficacy is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

The highest mean was 4.03 which means high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 1 – assuming that I can have excellent grades in math class. In contrast, the lowest mean was 3.89 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from items no. 5 – finding math as not a difficult subject.

Table 19. *Level of Mathematics Motivation in terms of Self-Efficacy*

<i>Self-Efficacy</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Assuming that I can have excellent grades in math class.	4.03	High
2. Thinking that I can understand the most difficult part in the math materials by my own.	3.90	High
3. Acknowledging the thought that I can master every topic in math class.	4.01	High
4. Believing that I am competent to teach my classmate in math.	3.90	High
5. Finding math as not a difficult subject.	3.89	High
Overall	3.95	High

Level of Mathematics Motivation in Terms of Test Anxiety

The level of mathematics motivation was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, test anxiety. The responses of first year to fourth year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 20 was the level of mathematics motivation in terms of test anxiety. The data revealed that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of test anxiety had a total mean of 4.02 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of test anxiety is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Table 20. *Level of Mathematics Motivation in terms of Test Anxiety*

<i>Test Anxiety</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Acknowledging negative thoughts when taking exams compared to my classmates.	3.97	High
2. Thinking continually about the questions I could not answer in previous part of the math exam.	4.03	High
3. Reflecting on the consequence of failing in the exam.	4.16	High
4. Experiencing a faster heartbeat while taking the math exam.	3.99	High
5. Struggling to get enough sleep before taking the exam.	3.96	High
Overall	4.02	High

The highest mean was 4.16 which means high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from item no. 1 – reflecting on the consequence of failing in the exam.

In contrast, the lowest mean was 3.96 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by first year to fourth year mathematics major students. This was from items no. 5 – struggling to get enough sleep before taking the exam.

Summary on the Level of Mathematics Motivation of the Students

Presented in Table 21 was the overall level of mathematics motivation in terms of intrinsic goal orientation, extrinsic goal orientation, task value, control beliefs for learning, self-efficacy and test anxiety. The data revealed that the level of student performance of mathematics major students has a total mean of 4.14 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of mathematics motivation of mathematics major students is oftentimes manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

Table 21. *Summary on the Level of Mathematics Motivation*

<i>Test Anxiety</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Intrinsic Goal Orientation	4.20	High
Extrinsic Goal Orientation	4.15	High
Task Value	4.22	High
Control Beliefs for Learning	4.34	Very High
Self-Efficacy	3.95	High
Test Anxiety	4.02	High
Overall	4.14	High

Further, the highest mean is 4.34 with the descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicated that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of control beliefs for learning is always manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

In contrast, the lowest indicator was self-efficacy which obtained a mean of 3.95 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of self-efficacy is oftentimes manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

In addition, extrinsic goal orientation obtained a mean of 4.15 which means high. This indicated that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of extrinsic goal orientation is oftentimes manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

However, intrinsic goal orientation obtained a mean of 4.20 which means high. This also indicated that the level of mathematics motivation in terms of intrinsic goal orientation is oftentimes manifested by first year to fourth year mathematics major students.

The task obtained a mean of 4.22, indicating a high level of importance. This indicated that mathematics motivation, in terms of task value, is oftentimes manifested among first year to fourth-year mathematics major students. The high mean reflects the significant value these students place on their mathematical tasks.

Significant Relationship Between Problem-solving Skills and Student Performance

Presented in Table 22 was the result of the significant relationship between problem-solving skills with a mean of 4.18 and student performance with a mean of 4.20, along with the $r(150)$ which from 152 respondents, now become 150, since the researcher measured two parameters in the study, the degree of freedom corresponds to the sample size (152) minus 2 since the researcher estimates two relationships.

Moreover, it also shown that the r -value is .849, it means that there is 84.9% of the variation of problem-solving skills which affects student performance. Nonetheless, the remaining 15.1% was based on the variables not covered on the study. Furthermore, the probability value ($p < .001$) was less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), which means null hypothesis is rejected. This indicated that there is a significant relationship between problem-solving skills and student performance.

Table 22. Significant Relationship between Problem-Solving Skills and Student Performance

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Problem-Solving Skills	4.18			
Student Performance	4.20	.849	<.001	Ho Rejected

Significant Relationship Between Problem-solving Skills and Mathematics Motivation

Presented in Table 23 was the result of the significant relationship between problem-solving skills with a mean of 4.18 and mathematics motivation with a mean of 4.14, along with the r (150) which from 152 respondents, now become 150, since the researcher measured two parameters in the study, the degree of freedom corresponds to the sample size (152) minus 2 since the researcher estimated two relationships. Moreover, it also showed that the r-value was .740, it means that there is 74.0% variation of problem-solving skills which affects student performance. Nonetheless, the remaining 26% was based on the variables not covered in the study. Furthermore, the probability value (p<.001) is less than the level of significance (α=0.05), which means null hypothesis is rejected. This indicated that there is a significant relationship between problem-solving skills and mathematics motivation.

Table 23. Significant Relationship between Problem-Solving Skills and Mathematics Motivation

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Problem-Solving Skills	4.18			
Mathematics Motivation	4.14	.740	<.001	Ho Rejected

Significant Relationship Between Student Performance and Mathematics Motivation

Presented in Table 24 was the result of the significant relationship between student performance with a mean of 4.20 and mathematics motivation with a mean of 4.20, along with the r (150) which from 152 respondents now become 150, since the researcher measured two parameters in the study, the degree of freedom corresponds to the sample size (152) minus 2 since the researcher estimates two relationships. Moreover, it also showed that the r-value was .839, it means that there is 83.9% of the variation of problem-solving skills which affects student performance. Nonetheless, the remaining 16.1% was based on the variables not covered in the study.

Furthermore, the probability value (p<.001) is less than the level of significance (α=0.05), which means null hypothesis is rejected. This indicated that there is a significant relationship between problem-solving skills and student performance.

Table 24. Significant Relationship between Student Performance and Mathematics Motivation

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Student Performance	4.20			
Mathematics Motivation	4.14	.839	<.001	Ho Rejected

Relationship of Problem-Solving Skills and Student Performance as Mediated by Mathematics Motivation Among Mathematics Major in Teacher Education Program

Preacher and Hayes mediation analysis approach was utilized in this study to determine if mathematics motivation mediates the relationship between problem-solving skills and student performance among mathematics major in teacher education program. It is a regression-based bootstrap approach similar to SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) that is used for analyzing mediation. It consists of two steps that reflect the recommendation for mediation analysis. In step 1, the direct and indirect effect are tested for significance. Step 2 involved defining the type of effect and mediation, which is classified into partial and full mediation.

Full mediation is achieved if the direct effect is not significant and the indirect effect is significant. It means that only the indirect effect via the mediator exists. On the other hand, partial mediation happens when the direct effect is significant.

Mediation Analysis

Direct Effect. Table 25 showed the direct effect of problem-solving skills (IV) on mathematics motivation (MV) is not significant [β=0.098, SE=0.084, 95% CI (-0.067, 0.263)]. Since the p-value is greater than the significance level 0.05 and the confidence interval does include zero, it indicated that the direct effect of problem-solving skills is not significant.

Table 25. Direct Effects

	Estimate	Std. Error	z- value	P	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
IV → MV	0.098	0.084	1.159	0.246	-0.067	0.263

Moreover, it can be observed that each unit increase the independent variable which is the problem-solving skills results in a 0.098 increase in the mediating variable which is the mathematics motivation with a p-value of .246. Therefore, it is revealed that the

problem-solving skills is not significantly influenced mathematics motivation, ($\beta=0.098$, $p=0.246$).

Indirect Effect. The table 26 showed the indirect effect of problem-solving skills (IV) on student performance (DV) and on mathematics motivation (MV) showed [$\beta=0.652$, $SE=0.079$, 95% CI (0.497, 0.806)].

Table 26. Indirect Effects

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
IV → DV → MV	0.652	0.079	8.273	<.001	0.497	0.806

Mathematics motivation has a statistically full mediating effect that represented by the coefficient β with the value 0.652. This means that each unit increase in the independent variable which is the problem-solving skills results in a 0.652 rise in the mediating variable which is the mathematics motivation through dependent variable which is the student performance. With a p-value of <.001 that is less than the significance level of 0.05, it indicated that the mediation effect is statistically significant, and with that evidence, the null hypothesis is not accepted. This announces that the mediating variable, which is the mathematics motivation, mediates the relationship between the independent variable, problem-solving skills, and the dependent variable, which is student performance.

Total Effect. Table 27 showed the total effect of problem-solving skills and on mathematics motivation (MV) showed [$\beta=0.749$]. It can be observed that every unit increased in the independent variable will results in a 0.749 rise in the mathematics motivation which is the mathematics motivation. This indicated that even without the presence of the dependent variable, student performance, problem-solving skills already affect mathematics motivation among mathematics education students. Since the direct effect is not significant, it can be concluded that the relationship between problem-solving skills and student performance is fully mediated by mathematics motivation.

Table 27. Total Effects

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
IV → MV	0.749	0.055	13.550	<.001	0.641	0.858

In the table 28 below showed that student performance (DV) had a significant effect on mathematics motivation (MV) and also with problem-solving skills (IV) on student performance (DV) but had no significant effect to problem-solving skills (IV) on mathematics motivation (MV). As the direct effect is statistically significant, however, the indirect effect is not significant, the mediation was fully mediated.

Table 28. Path coefficients

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
Student Performance → Mathematics Motivation	0.765	0.084	9.102	<.001	0.600	0.929
Problem-Solving Skills → Mathematics Motivation	0.098	0.084	1.159	0.246	-0.067	0.263
Problem-Solving Skills → Student Performance	0.852	0.043	19.838	<.001	0.768	0.937

Using Jasp program, the graph on figure 1 presented, mediation model was made. It showed relationship between problem-solving skills and student performance through mediating effect of mathematics motivation. In Path A, problem-solving skills (IV) has a significant relationship with student performance (DV), since p-value is <.001 which is less than 0.05 level of significance, which indicated that it has a significant relationship.

Figure 1. Path Plot Showing the Variables of the Study

In Path B, problem-solving skills (IV) found that it has no significant relationship with mathematics motivation (MV), since the p-value is .246 which is more than 0.05 significance level which indicated that it has no significant relationship. In Path C, mathematics motivation (MV) has a significant relationship with student performance (DV), since the p-value is .001 which is less than 0.05 significance level, this indicated that it has a significant relationship.

Conclusions

This section consists of the overall summary of the study, particularly the results and each of their implications. Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn in answer to the objectives:

The level of problem-solving skills as perceived by the mathematics major in teacher education program is high. Thus, acquiring problem-solving skills, would enhance their ability to comprehend and apply their skills in solving mathematical problem provided to them and empowered them to actively engage in educational process.

On the other hand, the level of student performance among mathematics major in teacher education program is high. Thus, consistently achieving good performances enables students to succeed in their chosen field and makes them challenge themselves and explore even more.

Moreover, the level of mathematics motivation among mathematics major in teacher education program who demonstrated mathematics motivation is also high. Thus, having motivation in mathematics enables student to obtain satisfaction from the subject, promoting a positive thinking and motivation towards educational exploration and understanding especially in mathematics discipline.

Based on the findings, there is a significant relationship between problem-solving skills and student performance, as it is affirmed that student performance in a general context is more likely to be affected by problem-solving skills. Therefore, as perceived by students, problem-solving skills immensely influenced the student performance, which stipulated a significant relationship between the two variables.

Based on the study's findings, there is also significant relationship between problem-solving skills and mathematics motivation. Therefore, students' mathematics motivation and problem-solving skills, as perceived by students are mutually reinforcing throughout their mathematics learning process. Therefore, as perceived by students, problem-solving skills is immensely influenced by their mathematics motivation, which stimulates a significant relationship between the two variables.

Also, there is a significant relationship between mathematics motivation and student performance. Therefore, effective mathematics motivation is emphasized when students perceived challenges and all the obstacles that comes along the way as areas that can be overcome through effort and acknowledgement. Therefore, mathematics motivation immensely influences the student performance, which stipulates a significant relationship between two variables.

Furthermore, the mediation analysis revealed that mathematics motivation has fully mediated the relationship between problem-solving skills and student performance. Therefore, the effectiveness of motivation in mathematics is intricately intertwined with the interplay of problem-solving skills, student performance and the adoption of effective mathematics motivation, collectively shaping the educational landscape and influencing students' academic achievements and overall mathematical proficiency. However, from the context of the results, these stipulate that the relationship between problem-solving skills and student performance is fully mediated by the direct pathway through mathematics motivation, a claim which opposite to the indirect effect.

The suggestions of the researcher were established based on the results and the wholeness of the paper. In light of the aforementioned findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

The level of problem-solving skills as perceived by mathematics major in teacher education program was high. However, among the items of each indicator of problem-solving skills, it was found that creative thinking was the item with the lowest mean result. It is therefore suggested that student should focus on developing a more systematic approach to problem-solving, such as enhancing skills in data analysis and organization to effectively utilize charts and tables, strengthening mathematical understanding to create personalized formulas for problem-solving, actively seeking and considering alternative problem-solving methods and strategies, improving planning and organization skills to develop comprehensive implementation plans, and enhancing visualization and creative thinking abilities to effectively utilize illustrations in problem-solving processes.

Moreover, the level of student performance among mathematics major in teacher education program was high. However, among the items of each indicator of student performance, it was found that strategic competence were the items with the lowest mean results. It is therefore suggested that the students consider seeking additional practice and guidance in each area. Utilize resources such as textbooks, online tutorials, and practice problems to strengthen understanding and skills. Additionally, consider seeking help from teachers or tutors who can provide personalized support and feedback. By dedicating focused effort and seeking appropriate assistance, proficiency in mathematical problem-solving can be enhanced.

Furthermore, the level of mathematics motivation among mathematics major in Teacher education program is high. However, among the items of each indicator of mathematics motivation, it was found that self-efficacy has the item with the lowest mean result. It is

therefore suggested that these students should make a reassessment and adjust expectations realistically. Consider seeking additional support and resources such as tutoring, supplemental materials, or study groups to strengthen understanding and skills. Emphasize the importance of consistent practice and seeking help when needed. Developing a growth mindset towards math, acknowledging areas for improvement, and adopting effective study habits can also contribute to improved performance and confidence in the subject.

Finally, as the mathematics motivation fully mediates the relationship between problem-solving skills and student performance, even though it is already fully mediated they are also encouraged to utilize other methodologies, factors, or variables that the study was not able to cover. Also, they might conduct it in other locales and/or with larger scale participants.

References

- Abdullah, A.H., Julius, E., Suhairom, N., Ali, M., Talib, C.A., Ashari, Z., Kohar, H., & Abh Rahman, S.N. (2022). Relationship between Self-Concept, Emotional Intelligence and Problem-Solving Skills on Secondary School Students' Attitude towards Solving Algebraic Problems. *Scholarly Journal: Sustainability*; Vol. 14, Iss. 21, (2022): 14402. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114402>
- Abuhamdeh, S. (2020). Investigating the "flow" experience: Key conceptual and operational issues. *Frontiers in psychology*, 11, 158. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00158/full>
- Adamma, O.N., Ekwutosim, O.P., & Unamba, E. (2018). Influence of Extrinsic and Intrinsic Motivation on Pupils Academic Performance in Mathematics. *SJME (Supremum Journal of Mathematics Education)* 2(2):52-59. <https://doi.org/10.35706/sjme.v2i2.1322>
- Aguilar-Luzón, M.C.; Calvo-Salguero, A.; Salinas, J.M. Beliefs and environmental behavior: The moderating effect of emotional intelligence. *Scand. J. Psychol.*; 2014; 55, pp. 619-629. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sjop.12160>
- Ajisuksmo, C. R. P., & Saputri, G. R. (2017). The influence of attitudes towards mathematics, and metacognitive awareness on mathematics achievements. *Creative Education*, 8, 486-497. 1, 1236. <https://doi.org/10.4236/CE.2017.83037>
- Ajisuksmo, C. R., & Saputri, G. R. (2017). The influence of attitudes towards mathematics, and metacognitive awareness on mathematics achievements. *Creative Education*, 8, 486, 497. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2017.83037>
- Akkaş, F. D., Aydin, S., Beydilli, A. B., Türnük, T., & Saydam, İ. (2020). Test anxiety in the foreign language learning context: A theoretical framework. *Focus on ELT Journal*, 2(1), 4-19. <https://doi.org/0.14744/felt.2020.00014>
- Al Husaini, Y. N. S., & Shukor, N. S. A. (2022). Factors affecting students' academic performance: A review. *RES MILITARIS*, 12(6), 284-294. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367360842_Factors_Affecting_Students'_Academic_Performance_A_review
- Alani, F. S., & Hawas, A. T. (2021). Factors affecting students academic performance: A case study of Sohar University. *Psychology and Education*, 58(5), 4624-4635. https://www.academia.edu/92736618/Factors_Affecting_Students_Academic_Performance_A_Case_Study_of_Sohar_University
- Albay, E. M. (2019). Analyzing the effects of the problem solving approach to the performance and attitude of first year university students. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 1(1), 100006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2019.100006>
- Alcantara, E. C., Bacsá, J. M. P., & City, B. (2018). Critical thinking and problem solving skills in mathematics of grade-7 public secondary students. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 5(4), 21-27. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326058813_Critical_Thinking_and_Problem_Solving_Skills_in_Mathematics_of_Grade-7_Public_Secondary_Students
- Al-Mutawah, M.A., Thomas, R., Eid, A., Mahmoud, E., & Fateel, M. (2019). CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING, PROCEDURAL KNOWLEDGE AND PROBLEMSOLVING SKILLS IN MATHEMATICS: HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATES WORK ANALYSIS AND STANDPOINTS. *International Journal of Education and Practice* (7), No. 3, pp. 258-273. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.61.2019.73.258.273>
- Alos, S. B., Caranto, L. C., & David, J. J. T. (2015). Factors affecting the academic performance of the student nurses of BSU. *International Journal of Nursing Science*, 5(2), 60-65. <https://doi.org/10.5923/j.nursing.20150502.04>
- Altarawneh, A.F. & Marei, S.T. (2021). Mathematical Proficiency and Preservice Classroom Teachers' Instructional Performance. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 9(2), <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.61.2021.92.354.364>
- Ambasa, R., & Tan, D. (2019). Student mathematics performance and problem-solving skills in an experiential learning environment. Unpublished Master's Thesis, Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Bukidnon. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360148973_Student_Mathematics_Performance_and_Problem-Solving_Skills_in_an_Experiential_Learning_Environment
- Andal, S. G. B., & Andrade, R. R. (2022). Exploring Students' Procedural Fluency and Written Adaptive Reasoning Skills in Solving Open-Ended Problems. *International Journal of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics*, 2(1), 1-25.

<https://doi.org/10.53378/352872>

Anthony, A. (2018). Factors contributing to the academic performance of students in junior high school. Retrieved from <https://www.grin.com/document/450284>

Ariella, S. (2023). The Most Important Research Skills (With Examples). <https://www.zippia.com/advice/research-skills/>

Awofala, A., Lawal, R., Arigbabu, A & Fatade, A. (2020). Mathematics productive disposition as a correlate of senior secondary school students' achievement in mathematics in Nigeria. *International Journal of Mathematical Education In Science & Technology* 53(1):1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2020.1815881>

Awofala, A.O., Lawani, A., & Adeyemi, O. (2020). Motivation to Learning Mathematics and Gender as Correlates of Senior Secondary School Students' Performance in Mathematics. *Journal Of Educational Sciences* 4(2):318. <https://doi.org/10.31258/jes.4.2.p.318-333>

Balka, H., & Miles, H. (2019). What Is Conceptual Understanding?, [online] retrieved www.mathleadership.com

Bamberg, S.; Möser, G. Twenty years after Hines, Hungerford, and Tomera: A new meta-analysis of psycho-social determinants of pro-environmental behaviour. *J. Environ. Psychol.*; 2007; 27, pp. 14-25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2006.12.002>

Baul A. L. N., Mahmud M. S. (2021). "Sentence-based mathematics problem solving skills in primary school mathematics learning: a literature review," in *International Virtual Conference on Education, Social Sciences and Technology 2021*, 3, 123–134. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9928858/#ref66>

Bay-Williams, J. M., & Stokes-Levine, A. (2017). Research-based Strategies that Build Procedural Fluency. Global Math Department. <https://globalmathdepartment.org/2017/07/research-based-strategies-that-build-procedural-fluency-jenny-bay-williams/>

Beltekin, E., & Kuyulu, I. (2020). Relationship between Digital Game Playing Motivation and Problem Solving Skill. *Asian Journal of Education and Training*, 6(2), 196-201. <https://doi.org/10.204448/journal.522.2020.62.196.201>

Birt, J. (2022). What Are Research Skills? Definition, Examples and Tips. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/research-skills>

Blankman, R. (2023). What Is Conceptual Understanding in Math?. <https://www.hmhco.com/blog/what-is-conceptual-understanding-in-math>

Bodner, G. M. (1986). Constructivism: A theory of knowledge. *Journal of chemical education*, 63(10), 873. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ed063p873>

Brunstein, J. C., & Heckhausen, H. (2018). Achievement motivation. *Motivation and action*, 221-304. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-65094-4_6

Buela, M., Joaquin, M. N., Tandang, N., & Bulasag, A. (2021). Association of ambiguity tolerance and problem-solving ability of students in mathematics. *International Journal of Sciences Basic and Applied Research*, 51(1), 12-24. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ma-Nympha-Joaquin/publication/348787324_Association_of_Ambiguity_Tolerance_and_Problem-solving_Ability_of_Students_in_Mathematics

Cain, T., Brindley, S., Brown, C., Jones, G., & Riga, F. (2019). Bounded decision-making, teachers' reflection and organisational learning: How research can inform teachers and teaching. *British Educational Research Journal*, 45(5), 1072-1087. <https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3551>

Campos, C.B.d.; Pol, E. Can the environmental beliefs of workers from environmental certified companies predict their environmental behavior outside the organization?. *Estud. De Psicol.*; 2010; 15, pp. 198-206. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S1413-294X2010000200009>

Carr, E., Reece, A., Kellerman, G. R., & Robichaux, A. (2019). The Value of Belonging at Work. https://cdn.ymaws.com/www.sdshrm.org/resource/resmgr/resourceblog/The_Value_of_Belonging_at_Wo.PDF

Casali, G. L., & Perano, M. (2021). Forty years of research on factors influencing ethical decision making: Establishing a future research agenda. *Journal of Business Research*, 132, 614-630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.07.006>

Chand S, Chaudhary K, Prasad A and Chand V. (2021). Perceived Causes of Students' Poor Performance in Mathematics: A Case Study at Ba and Tavua Secondary Schools. *Front. Appl. Math. Stat.* 7:614408. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fams.2021.614408>

Chen, W. and Ho, H. (2012). The relation between perceived parental involvement and academic achievement: the roles of taiwanese students' academic beliefs and filial piety. *International Journal of Psychology*, 47(4), 315-324. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207594.2011.630004>

Cherry, K. (2023). What is Test Anxiety. *Verywell Mind*. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-test-anxiety-2795368#citation-4>

Cipriano, C., Strambler, M. J., Naples, L. H., Ha, C., Kirk, M., Wood, M., & Durlak, J. (2023). The state of evidence for social and

emotional learning: A contemporary meta-analysis of universal school-based SEL interventions. *Child Development*, 94(5), 1181-1204. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13968>

Cole, L. (2021). Definition of Analytical Thinking and Analytical Skills. <https://www.mentalup.co/blog/what-is-analytical-thinking-ability-and-how-to-develop>

Csikszentmihalyi, M., Montijo, M. N., & Mouton, A. R. (2018). Flow theory: Optimizing elite performance in the creative realm. In S. I. Pfeiffer, E. Shaunessy-Dedrick, & M. Foley-Nicpon (Eds.), *APA handbook of giftedness and talent* (pp. 215–229). American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0000038-014>

Darwani., Zubaaainur, C.M., & Saminan. (2020). Adaptive reasoning and strategic competence through problem-based learning model in middle school. *Phys.: Conf. Ser.* 1460 012019. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1460/1/012019>

Dayaganon, C., Elladora, S., Carreon, M., & Bustamante, J.L. (2022). Perceived Level of Competence of the University Students' Problem-Solving Skills in Mathematics in the New Normal. *International Journal of Educational Science and Research (IJESR)* ISSN (P): 2249-6947; ISSN (E): 2249-8052 12 (1), Jun 2022, 173–188, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367022006_PERCEIVED_LEVEL_OF_COMPETENCE_OF_THE_UNIVERSITY_STUDENTS%27_PROBLEM-SOLVING_SKILLS_IN_MATHEMATICS_IN_THE_NEW_NORMAL

Dayupay, J. P., Velos, S. P., Go, M. B., Cababat, F. G., & Golbin Jr, R. A. (2022). College Students' Motivational Strategies, Study Skills, and Mathematics Performance: A Structural Model. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 2246-2264. <http://mail.journalppw.com/index.php/jpsp/article/view/6290>

de Andreis, F. (2020). A Theoretical Approach to the Effective Decision-Making Process. *Open Journal of Applied Sciences > Vol.10 No.6*. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.4236/ojapps.2020.106022>

Denkci Akkaş, F., Aydın, S., Baştürk Beydilli, A., Türnük, T. & Saydam, İ. (2020). Test Anxiety in the Foreign Language Learning Context: A Theoretical Framework. *Focus on ELT Journal (FELT)*, 2(1), 4-19. <https://doi.org/10.14744/felt.2020.00014>

Denkci Akkaş, F., Aydın, S., Baştürk Beydilli, A., Türnük, T. ., & Saydam, İlknur. (2020). Test Anxiety in the Foreign Language Learning Context: A Theoretical Framework . *Focus on ELT Journal*, 2(1), 4–19. <https://doi.org/10.14744/felt.2020.00014>

Denzin, N., & Lincoln, Y. (2011). *The SAGE handbook of qualitative research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE. <https://us.sagepub.com/en-us/nam/the-sage-handbook-of-qualitative-research/book242504>

Dewi, I. K., Waluya, S. B., & Firmasari, S. (2020, April). Adaptive reasoning and procedural fluency in three-dimensional. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1511, No. 1, p. 012101). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1511/1/012101>

Ebrahimi, M. R., & Khoshsima, I. H. (2018). Impact of Emotional Intelligence Enhancement on Test Anxiety among EFL Learners: an Experimental Study. *International Journal of English Language & Translation Studies*, 4(1), 136-145. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Impact-of-Emotional-Intelligence-Enhancement-on-EFL-Ebrahimi>

Eccles, J. S., & Wigfield, A. (2020). From expectancy-value theory to situated expectancy-value theory: A developmental, social cognitive, and sociocultural perspective on motivation. *Contemporary educational psychology*, 61, 101859. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101859>

Edulsa, V. (2022). Conceptual Understanding and Academic Performance of Students in Mathematics. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 5(9), 737-746. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7352844>

Egunsola, A. O. E. (2019). Influence of home environment on academic performance of secondary school students in agricultural science in Adamawa State Nigeria. *Journal of Research and Method in Education*, 4(4), 46-53. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Influence-of-Home-Environment-on-Academic-of-School-Egunsola/cc61804f584ab253a660439d1d506e052398c7ea>

Elhassan, M., Tharbe, I., & Muhamad, A. (2021). The direct and indirect effects of implicit beliefs of intelligence on academic achievement in english among high school students: goal orientation as a mediator. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, 19(54), 247-272. <https://doi.org/10.25115/ejrep.v19i54.3584>

Elhassan, M., Tharbe, I., & Muhamad, A. (2021). The direct and indirect effects of implicit beliefs of intelligence on academic achievement in english among high school students: goal orientation as a mediator. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, 19(54), 247-272. <https://doi.org/10.25115/ejrep.v19i54.3584>

Elsayed, S.A. (2022). "The Effectiveness of Learning Mathematics according to the STEM Approach in Developing the Mathematical Proficiency of Second Graders of the Intermediate School", *Education Research International*, vol. 2022, Article ID 5206476, 10 pages, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/5206476>

Estrada, M.; Monferrer, D.; Rodríguez, A.; Moliner, M.Á. Does emotional intelligence influence academic performance? The role of

compassion and engagement in education for sustainable development. *Sustainability*; 2021; 13, 1721. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13041721>

European Council Recommendation. (2018). On promoting common values, inclusive education, and the European dimension of teaching. Official Journal of the European Union. [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018H0607\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018H0607(01))

Farrukh, M.; Raza, A.; Mansoor, A.; Khan, M.S.; Lee, J.W.C (2022). Trends and patterns in pro-environmental behaviour research: A bibliometric review and research agenda. *Benchmarking Int. J.*; 2022; <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-10-2020-0521>

Firdaus, A., Sujadi, I., & Indriati, D. (2019). Characteristic profile of analytical thinking in mathematics problem solving. *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* 1157 032123. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1157/3/032123>

Fuertes, H., Evangelista Jr, I., Marcellones, I. J., & Bacatan, J. (2023). Student Engagement, Academic Motivation, and Academic Performance of Intermediate Level Students. *International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning*, 10(1), 133-149. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8037103>

Fuqoha, A.A., Budiyono, B & Indriati, D. (2018). Motivation in Mathematics Learning. <https://doi.org/10.25037/pancaran.v7i1.151>

Galate, R., & Galate, M. (2022). Problem-Solving And Decision-Making Skills of School Administrators Influenced by their Individual Preferences. *Journal for Educators, Teachers and Trainers*, Vol. 14 (1). <https://doi.org/10.47750/jett.2023.14.01.023>

Gavin, M. (2020). 5 key decision-making techniques for managers. *Business insights*. <https://online.hbs.edu/blog/post/decision-making-techniques>

Gilbert, M. (2018). Student performance is linked to connecting effectively with teachers. *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching & Learning*, 12(3), 311-324. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRIT-05-2018-0010>

Gillison, F., Rouse, P., Standage, M., Sebire, S., & Ryan, R. M. (2019). A meta-analysis of techniques to promote motivation for health behaviour change from a self-determination theory perspective. *Health Psychology Review*, 13(1), 110-130. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17437199.2018.1534071>

Giulioni, J. W. (2019). Are you a reflective or reflexive leader? Smart brief. <https://www.smartbrief.com/original/2019/02/are-you-reflective-or-reflexive-leader>.

Go, M. C. J., & Lomibao, L. S. (2024). EXPLORING LEARNERS'PRODUCTIVE DISPOSITION TOWARDS LEARNING MATHEMATICS: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL ANALYSIS. [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378008424_Good, H. \(2023\). What are research skills?. https://dovetail.com/research/research-skills/](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378008424_Good, H. (2023). What are research skills?. https://dovetail.com/research/research-skills/)

Goodrich, R. (2021). What are Research Skills and why are they important?. <https://aofirs.org/articles/what-are-research-skills-and-why-are-they-important>

Gözcü Reyhan, Ö. (2018). Investigation of the relationship between creative thinking tendencies, perceptions of problem solving and academic achievement of eighth grade primary school students. Çukurova University, Adana, Turkey. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1292178.pdf>

Grady, M. (2016). Maureen Grady. (2016). Whatever Happened to Productive Disposition? *Mathematics Teaching in the Middle School*, 21(9), 516–518. <https://doi.org/10.5951/mathteachmidscho.21.9.0516>

Green, Z. A. (2020). The mediating effect of well-being between generalized self-efficacy and vocational identity development. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Guidance*, 20(2), 215-241. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10775-019-09401-7>

Guinocor, M., Almerino, Jr., Mamites, I., Lumayag, C., & Villaganas, M. (2020). Mathematics Performance of Students in a Philippine State University. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*. 15(3). <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/7859>

Gülen, H., & Peker, A. (2018). Investigation of the relationships between adolescents' problem-solving skills and cyberbullying coping behaviors. *Bayburt Journal of Education Faculty*, 13(26), 385-404. A preliminary y exploratory study with a focus on secondary School students. <https://doi.org/10.29329/ijpe.2020.329.20>

Gürbüz, O. C. A. K., Doğruel, A. B., & Tepe, M. E. (2021). An analysis of the relationship between problem solving skills and scientific attitudes of secondary school students. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 8(1), 72-83. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1292178.pdf>

Hagger, M., Gucciardi, F., Turrell, A., & Hamilton, K. (2019). Self-control and health-related behaviour: The role of implicit self-control, trait self-control, and lay beliefs in self-control. *British Journal of Health Psychology* 24(4):764-786. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjhp.12378>

Haji, S. (2019). Improving Students' Productive Disposition through Realistic Mathematics Education with Outdoor Approach. *Journal*

of Research and Advances in Mathematics Education, 4(2), 101-111. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691617697078>

Haji, S., & Yumiati, Y. (2019). Improving Students' Productive Disposition through Realistic Mathematics Education with Outdoor Approach. *JRAMathEdu (Journal of Research and Advances in Mathematics Education)* 4(2):101-111. <https://doi.org/10.23917/jramathedu.v4i2.8385>

Harappa (2020). The Importance of Teamwork. <https://harappa.education/harappa-diaries/teamwork-and-its-importance/>

Harris & Robert (2016). "Introduction to Creative Thinking." Virtual Salt. Retrieved from <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/suny-collegesuccess-lumen1/chapter/creative-thinking-skills/3>

Hassan, M., Nawaz, H., & Akbar, R.A. (2021). Teachers Self-Efficacious, Locus Of Control And Workplace Spirituality Beliefs Buffers The Effects On Elementary Students Achievement Scores. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews* 9(3):272-285. <https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2021.9328>

Hassan, N., & Rahman, S. (2017). Problem Solving Skills, Metacognitive Awareness, and Mathematics Achievement: A Mediation Model. *The New Educational Review* 49(3):201-212. <https://doi.org/10.15804/ner.2017.49.3.16>

Herges, R., Duffield, S., Martin, W., & Wageman, J. (2017). Motivation and Achievement of Middle School Mathematics Students. *The Mathematics Educator* 2017 Vol. 26, No. 1, 83–106. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1153299.pdf>

Hidayat, R., Nugroho, I., Zainuddin, Z., & Ingai, T. A. (2023). A systematic review of analytical thinking skills in STEM education settings. *Information and Learning Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ils-06-2023-0070>

Ho, T.M. (2020). Measuring Conceptual Understanding, Procedural Fluency and Integrating Procedural and Conceptual Knowledge in Mathematical Problem Solving. *International Journal of scientific research and management*, 8, 1334-1350. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijstrm/v8i05.el02>

Ho, T.M. (2020). Measuring Conceptual Understanding, Procedural Fluency and Integrating Procedural and Conceptual Knowledge in Mathematical Problem Solving. *International Journal of scientific research and management*, 8, 1334-1350. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341317806_Measuring_Conceptual_Understanding_Procedural_Fluency_and_Integrating_Procedural_and_Conceptual_Knowledge_in_Mathematical_Problem_Solving

Hossein-Mohand, H., & Hossein-Mohand, H. (2023). Influence of motivation on the perception of mathematics by secondary school students. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 1111600. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1111600>

Huber, C. R., & Kuncel, N. R. (2016). Does college teach critical thinking? A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 86(2), 431-468. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654315605917>

Hutajulu, M., Wijaya, T. T., & Hidayat, W. (2019). The effect of mathematical disposition and learning motivation on problem solving: an analysis. *Infinity Journal*, 8(2), 229-238. <https://doi.org/10.22460/infinity.v8i2.p229-238>

Ilyas, M., Ma'rufi, M., Fitriani, F., & Salwal, S. (2018). Analysis of senior high school students' emotional intelligence in cooperative based mathematics learning. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series; Bristol Vol. 1088, Iss. 1*. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1088/1/012082>

Ilyas, M., Ma'rufi., & Basir, F. (2019). Students metacognitive skill in learning mathematics through cooperative based emotional intelligence. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series; Bristol Vol. 1397, Iss. 1*. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1397/1/012089>.

Inayah, S., Septian, A., & Suwarman, R. F. (2020). Student procedural fluency in numerical method subjects. *Desimal: Jurnal Matematika*, 3(1), 53-64. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339026482_Student_Procedural_Fluency_in_Numerical_Method_Subjects

Ince, E. (2018). An overview of problem solving studies in physics education. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 7(4), 191. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jel.v7n4p191>

Indeed Editorial Team. (2024). Research Skills: Definition, Examples and Importance. <https://sg.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/research-skills>

Inggriyani, F. and Hamdani, A. (2019). Self-regulated learning and academic achievement among elementary school students. <https://doi.org/10.2991/aes-18.2019.67>

Inggriyani, F., & Hamdani, A.R. (2019). Self-Regulated Learning and Academic Achievement Among Elementary School Students. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 253. <https://doi.org/10.2991/aes-18.2019.67>

Janowiak, A. (2019). Teamwork: Solving Problems. <https://www.conovercompany.com/teamwork-solving-problems/>

Jazuli, A. & Setyosari, Punaji & Sulthon, & Kuswandi, Dedi. (2019). Improving conceptual understanding and problem-solving in

mathematics through a contextual learning strategy. *Global Journal of Engineering Education*. 19. 49-53. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323111425_Improving_conceptual_understanding_and_problemsolving_in_mathematics_through_a_contextual_learning_strategy/citation/download

Johnson, C. K., Gutzwiller, R. S., Ferguson-Walter, K. J., & Fugate, S. J. (2020). A cyber-relevant table of decision making biases and their definitions. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.14891.87846>.

Joseph, D. L., Jin, J., Newman, D. A., & O'Boyle, E. H. (2015). Why does self-reported emotional intelligence predict job performance? A meta-analytic investigation of mixed EI. *Journal of applied psychology*, 100(2), 298. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Why-does-self-reported-emotional-intelligence-job-A-Joseph-Jin/eea29b2023eff0e202cb007021b724c2a110bed4>

Julizal, T., Johar, R., & Hizir. (2021). Creative thinking in mathematics: The capacity of vocational school students. *SEA-STEM 2020 Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 1882 (2021) 012053. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1882/1/012053>

Kaleli, Y. (2020). Investigation of the relationship between pre-service music teachers' attitudes towards teaching profession and their self-efficacy beliefs. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science*, 6(4), 580. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijres.v6i4.1493>

Kaleli, Y.S. (2020). Investigation of the Relationship between Pre-service Music Teachers' Attitudes towards Teaching Profession and their Self-efficacy Beliefs. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science* 6(4):580. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijres.v6i4.1493>

Karim, K. and Tajibu, M. (2021). The influence of emotional motives on the decision to use a credit card. *Hasanuddin Economics and Business Review*, 5(2), 41. <https://doi.org/10.26487/hebr.v5i2.2951>

Kartikasari, SA., Usodo, B., Riyadi. (2022). The Effectiveness Open-Ended learning and Creative Problem Solving Models to Teach Creative Thinking Skills. *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, Vol. 12, No. 4, 2022 (pp. 29-38). <https://doi.org/10.47750/pegegog.12.04.04>

Ke, H., Junfeng, D., & Xiaojing, L. (2022). International students' university choice to study abroad in higher education and influencing factors analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 1036569. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1036569>

Kenni, A. M. (2020). Analysis of Students' Performance in Chemistry in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and National Examination Council (NECO) from 2015-2018. *IJRAR-International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 7(1), 35-49. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Analysis-of-Students%E2%80%99-Performance-in-Chemistry-in-Kenni/4a8adbce43bcc6c4f12e152be5a01bb65d968d7e>

Khalil, I. A., & Prahmana, R. C. I. (2024). Mathematics Learning Orientation: Mathematical Creative Thinking Ability or Creative Disposition?. *Journal on Mathematics Education*, 15(1), 253-276. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1413546.pdf>

Khatimah, H., & Sugiman, S. (2019). The Effect Of Problem Solving Approach To Mathematics Problem Solving Ability In Fifth Grade. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series; Bristol* Vol. 1157. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1157/4/042104>

Khusna, AH. (2020). Analytical Thinking Process Of Student In Proving Mathematical Argument. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC & TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH* (9), ISSUE 01. <https://www.ijstr.org/final-print/jan2020/-Analytical-Thinking-Process-Of-Student-In-Proving-Mathematical-Argument.pdf>

King, B. (2019). Using Teaching through Problem Solving to Transform In-Service Teachers' Thinking about Instruction. *Mathematics Teacher Education and Development*, 21(1), 169-189. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1216039.pdf>

Klang, N., Karlsson, N., Kilborn, W., Eriksson, P., & Karlberg, M. (2021, August). Mathematical problem-solving through cooperative learning—the importance of peer acceptance and friendships. In *Frontiers in Education* (Vol. 6, p. 710296). *Frontiers*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2021.710296>

Kolmar, C. (2021, May 17). The most important Decision-Making skills (with examples) – zippia. Retrieved May 29, 2021, from <https://www.zippia.com/advice/decision-making-skills/>

Kozlowski, S. W. (2018). Enhancing the effectiveness of work groups and teams: A reflection. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 13(2), 205-212.

Kuncorowati, R & Mardiyana, Mardiyana & Saputro, Dewi. (2017). Mathematics creative thinking levels based on interpersonal intelligence. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. 943. 012005. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/943/1/012005>.

Kusmaryono, I., Suyitno, H., Dwijanto, D & Dwidayati, N. (2019). The Effect of Mathematical Disposition on Mathematical Power Formation: Review of Dispositional Mental Functions. *International Journal of Instruction*, 12 (1) 343-356. https://www.e-iji.net/dosyalar/iji_2019_1_23.pdf

Lauran, C. (2021). Definition of Analytical Thinking and Analytical Skills. <https://www.mentalup.co/blog/what-is-analytical-thinking->

ability-and-how-to-develop.

Lee, J. (2022). Structural relationships between cognitive achievement and learning-related factors among south korean adolescents. *Journal of Intelligence*, 10(4), 81. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jintelligence10040081>

Leng, L. (2020). The role of philosophical inquiry in helping students engage in learning. *Frontiers in psychology*, 11, 519240. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00449/full>

Lester, D. (2022). Factors influencing civil engineering university students' decision making. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 47(6), 970-985. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2022.2052810>

Liu, Eric., & Lin, Chun Hung (2010). The Survey Study Of Mathematics Motivated Strategies For Learning Questionnaire (Mmslq) For Grade 10–12 Taiwanese Students. *TOJET: The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 9(2), https://www.researchgate.net/publication/232716617_The_survey_study_of_mathematics_motivated_strategies_for_learning_questionnaire_MMSLQ_for_grade_10-12_Taiwanese_students/link/09e41508f29cb216ac000000/download

Liu, T., & Lipowski, M. (2021). Influence of Cooperative Learning Intervention on the Intrinsic Motivation of Physical Education Students—A Meta-Analysis within a Limited Range. *Neuroeducation, Motivation and Physical Activity in Students of Physical Education*. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/18/6/2989>

Liu, Y., Hau, K., Liu, H., & Wu, J. (2019). Multiplicative effect of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on academic performance: A longitudinal study of Chinese students. *Journal of Personality* 88(3). <https://doi.org/10.1111/jopy.12512>

Liu, Z., Li, S., Shang, S., & Ren, X. (2021). How do critical thinking ability and critical thinking disposition relate to the mental health of university students?. *Frontiers in psychology*, 12, 704229. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.704229>

Llagas Jr, R. M. (2021). Prospective Filipino Teachers' Disposition to Mathematics. *Mathematics and Statistics*, 9(2), 93-97. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ms.2021.090202>

Louw, E. (2021). Conceptual understanding in mathematics, its importance, and how to teach it. <https://relearnmath.com/conceptual-understanding-its-importance-and-how-to-teach-it/>

Lune, H., & Berg, B. L. (2017). *Qualitative research methods for the social sciences*. Pearson. https://books.google.com.ph/books/about/Qualitative_Research_Methods_for_the_Soc.html?id=6E_gjwEACAAJ&redir_esc=y

Lyman, A.L. (2022). Procedural fluency in mathematics: Exploring elementary teachers' knowledge, understanding, and application in classroom practices. <https://krex.kstate.edu/bitstream/handle/2097/42852/AllysonLyman2022.pdf?sequence=5>

MacKinnon, D. P., Fairchild, A. J., & Fritz, M. S. (2007). Mediation analysis. *Annu. Rev. Psychol.*, 58(1), 593-614. <https://www2.psych.ubc.ca/~schaller/528Readings/MacKinnonFairchildFritz2007.pdf>

Magano, J.; Silva, C.; Figueiredo, C.; Vitória, A.; Nogueira, T.; Pimenta Dinis, M.A. (2020). Generation Z: Fitting Project Management Soft Skills Competencies—A Mixed-Method Approach. *Educ. Sci.* 2020, 10, 187. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343105796_Generation_Z_Fitting_Project_Management_Soft_Skills_Competencies-A_Mixed-Method_Approach

Mamona-Downs, j., & Downs, M. (2013). Problem Solving and its elements in forming proof. *The Mathematics Enthusiast*: 10 (1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.54870/1551-3440.1263>

Marinda, L. (2020). "Jean Piaget's Theory of Cognitive Development and Its Problems in Elementary School Age Children,". *Pusat Studi Gender dan Anak (PSGA) LP2M IAIN Jember*, 13 (1), pp. 116–152, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.35719/annisa.v13i1.26>

Masitoh, L. F., & Fitriyani, H. (2018). Improving students' mathematics self-efficacy through problem based learning. *Malikussaleh Journal of Mathematics Learning (MJML)*, 1(1), 26-30. <https://doi.org/10.29103/mjml.v1i1.679>

Mayer, J.D. (2000). Educational policy on emotional intelligence: Does it make sense?. *Educ. Psychol. Rev.* 12, pp. 163-183. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1009093231445>.

Mcleod, S. (2023). *Constructivism learning theory & philosophy of education*. Simply Psychology. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/constructivism.html>

Mihye, L. (2020). Effectiveness of simulation linked problem based learning on nursing college students in south korea. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 9(2), 15. <https://doi.org/10.36941/ajis-2020-0018>

Miller, A., Horton, C., Koscheka, C., & Murray, C. (2022). Anxiety, motivation, and academic achievement in underrepresented groups. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/B9780323914970001107?via%3Dihub>

Milou, E. (2021). 5 Critical Components For Mathematical Proficiency. <https://blog.savvas.com/5-critical-components-for->

mathematical-proficiency/

Miltsakaki, E. (2012). A study of students poor research skills as demonstrated in a record of search behavior on the internet. In Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference (pp. 3701-3706). Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259669017_A_study_of_students%27_research_skills_as_demonstrated_in_a_record_of_search_behavior_on_the_internet

Miltsakaki, E. (2012, March). A study of students poor research skills as demonstrated in a record of search behavior on the internet. In Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference (pp. 3701-3706). Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259669017_A_study_of_students%27_research_skills_as_demonstrated_in_a_record_of_search_behavior_on_the_internet

Minarti, E.D., & Wahyudin, W. (2019). Conceptual understanding and mathematical disposition of college student through concrete-representational-abstract approach (CRA), Journal of Physics: Conference Series 1157(4): 042124. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1157/4/042124>

Ministry of Education and Vocational Training. (2019). I Plan Estratégico: Formación Profesional del Sistema Educativo 2019–2022. [I Strategic Plan: Vocational Training of the Educational System 2019-2022]. <https://www.educacionyfp.gob.es/dam/jcr:1bc3728e-d71f-4a8e-bb99-846996d8a2f2/iplan-estrat-gico-de-formaci-n-profesional-del-sistema.pdf>

Mohammed, B.I., & Maude, L. (2022). Comparative Analysis of Students' Performance in WAEC and NECO. Comparative Analysis of Students' Performance in WAEC and NECO English Language and General Mathematics Examinations of Senior Secondary Schools in Kano State, Nigeria. 8. 480-487. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369688345_Comparative_Analysis_of_Students'_Performance_in_WAEC_and_NECO_Comparative_Analysis_of_Students'_Performance_in_WAEC_and_NECO_English_Language_and_General_Mathematics_Examinations_of_Senior_Secondary_Schools_in_Kano_State_Nigeria

Morgan, O. (2019). How decision makers can use quantitative approaches to guide outbreak responses. Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B, 374(1776), 20180365. <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/10.1098/rstb.2018.0365>

Mousoulides, N., & Sriraman, B. (2020). Mathematical Games in Learning and Teaching. Encyclopedia of Mathematics Education. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-15789-0_97

Muin, A., Hanifah, S. H., & Diwidian, F. (2018). The effect of creative problem solving on students' mathematical adaptive reasoning. Journal of Physics: Conference Series. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/948/1/012001>

Naber, J., & Wyatt, T. H. (2014). The effect of reflective writing interventions on the critical thinking skills and dispositions of baccalaureate nursing students. Nurse Education Today, 34(1), 67-72. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/The-effect-of-reflective-writing-interventions-on-Naber-Wyatt/3edb2e2ef589db8169c69d0c715cce0dc1cffad5>

Nahdi, D.S., & Jatisunda, M.G. (2020). Conceptual Understanding And Procedural Knowledge: A Case Study on Learning Mathematics of Fractional Material in Elementary School. Journal of Physics: Conference Series 1477, 042037. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1477/4/042037>

National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM). 2020. Catalyzing Change in Early Childhood and Elementary Mathematics: Initiating Critical Conversations. Reston, VA: NCTM. <https://www.nctm.org/Standards-and-Positions/Catalyzing-Change/Catalyzing-Change-in-Early-Childhood-and-Elementary-Mathematics/>

National Council of Teachers of Mathematics [NCTM] (2023). Reasoning and Decision-Making, Not Rote Application of Procedures Position. <https://www.nctm.org/Standards-and-Positions/Position-Statements/Procedural-Fluency-in-Mathematics/>

Navdeep (2020). Research skills. <https://www.beetroot.com/graduate-jobs/careers-advice/research-skills/>

Nogueira, T., Castro, R., & Magano, J. (2023). Engineering Students Education in Sustainability: The Moderating Role of Emotional Intelligence. Scholarly Journal: Sustainability; Basel Vol. 15, Iss. 6, (2023): 5389. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15065389>

Ocak, G., & EĞMiR, E. (2019). The relationship between pre-service teachers' critical thinking tendencies and problem solving skills. Participatory Educational Research, 3(5), 33-44. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/288072461_The_Relationship_Between_PreService_Teachers'_Critical_Thinking_Tendencies_and_Problem_Solving_Skills

Oco, R., Jade S. (2023). Students' Mathematical Skills and Performance. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373110709_Students'_Mathematical_Skills_and_Performance

Onokala, U.; Banwo, A.O.; Okeowo, F.O. Predictors of Pro-Environmental Behavior: A Comparison of University Students in the Hormillada & Jajalla

United States and China. *J. Manag. Sustain.* 2018 (8), 127. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jms.v8n1p127>

Öztürk, M., Akkan, Y., & Kaplan, A. (2020). Reading comprehension, Mathematics self-efficacy perception, and Mathematics attitude as correlates of students' non-routine Mathematics problem-solving skills in Turkey. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 51(7), 1042-1058. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2019.1648893>

Palmer, P. (2023). The Importance of Motivation in the Pharmaceutical Industry. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-motivation-pharmaceutical-industry-paul-palmer-0ypxe>

Pearson, R. W. (2010). *Statistical persuasion: How to collect, analyze, and present data... accurately, honestly, and persuasively*. Sage. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452230122>

Peldon, S., & Lynch, R. (2022). The Relationship Of Intrinsic Goal Orientation For Learning Geography, Self-Efficacy For Learning And Performance In Geography, And Metacognitive Self-Regulated Geography Learning With Bhutan Geography Achievement Of Grade 8 Students At Druk Higher Secondary School In Thimphu, Bhutan. <https://repository.au.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams/03276ece-021b-4906-83e2-81bd4b9e9735/content>

Peñeda, F. P., & Ticoy, T. A. (2019). Filipino Students' Perceptions of Factors Affecting Their Academic Performance in School: A Qualitative Study. *Journal of Education and Society*, 3(1), 19-30. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5559205>

Perry, E. (2022). What will make or break your next role? Find out why teamwork matters. <https://www.betterup.com/blog/what-is-teamwork>

Piaget, J. (1964). Part I: Cognitive development in children: Piaget development and learning. *Journal Research in Science Teaching*, 2(3), 176–186. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.3660020306>

Pishghadam, R., Faribi, M., Kolahi Ahari, M., Shadloo, F., Gholami, M.J., & Shayesteh, S. (2022). Intelligence, emotional intelligence, and emo-sensory intelligence: Which one is a better predictor of university students' academic success? *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.995988>

Prada, E. D., Mareque, M., & Pino-Juste, M. (2022). Teamwork skills in higher education: is university training contributing to their mastery?. *Psicologia: Reflexao e critica*, 35, 5. <https://prc.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s41155-022-00207-1>

Qolfathiriyus, A., Sujadi, I. & Indriati, D., (2019). Students' Analytical Thinking Profile Based on Reflective Cognitive Style in Solving Mathematics Problem. *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* 1306 012016. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1306/1/012016>

Rach, S. (2022). Motivational states in an undergraduate mathematics course: relations between facets of individual interest, task values, basic needs, and effort. *ZDM: the international journal on mathematics education* 55(5). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-022-01406-x>

Rasmuin, Jais, E., & Sardin. (2019). The Effect of Mathematics Learning With using Reciprocal Teaching Model on Mathematics Creative Thinking Ability. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 1477 (2020) 042041. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1477/4/042041>

Richardson, A. D. (2020). *Examining Leadership and Emotional Intelligence of Police Leaders in Rural Policing Agencies* (Doctoral dissertation, Capella University). [https://www.proquest.com/openview/743f5bc4b418ec7ea4051126c91f9b5a/1?pq](https://www.proquest.com/openview/743f5bc4b418ec7ea4051126c91f9b5a/1?pq-origsite=scholarlink)

Rizal, S., Munawir, M., U. Sulistyawati, U.S., & Jamil, M. (2020). "Self-Ability Development through the Interest and Talent Test of Vocational High School Students". *ETHOS: Jurnal Penelitian dan Pengabdian kepada Masyarakat*, 8(2). <http://doi.org/10.29313/ethos.v8i2.5927>

Rohmah, M., & Sutiarmo, S. (2018). Analysis problem solving in mathematical using theory Newman. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education* (2018) 14(2) 671-681. <https://doi.org/10.12973/ejmste/80630>

Rojo Robas, V., Madariaga, J.M., & Villarroel, J.D. (2020). *Secondary Education*

Roos, A. L., Goetz, T., Voracek, M., Krannich, M., Bieg, M., Jarrell, A., & Pekrun, R. (2021). Test anxiety and physiological arousal: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33, 579-618. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-020-09543-z>

Ryan, R., & Deci, E. (2020). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation from a self-determination theory perspective: Definitions, theory, practices, and future directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101860>

Saadati, F., & Celis, S. (2022). Student Motivation in Learning Mathematics in Technical and Vocational Higher Education: Development of an Instrument. *International Journal of Education in Mathematics Science and Technology* In press(1). <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijemst.2194>

Saadati, F., & Celis, S. (2023). Student motivation in learning mathematics in technical and vocational higher education: Development of an instrument. *International Journal of Education in Mathematics, Science, and Technology (IJEMST)*, 11(1), 156-178.

<https://doi.org/10.46328/ijemst.2194>

Sabanal, G. J. A., Reputana, K. G. D., Palwa, S. S., Labandero, C. L. H., & Alimbon, J. A. (2023). Motivation and Academic Performance of Secondary Students in Science: A Correlational Study. *Asian Journal of Science Education*, 5(2), 20-29. <https://doi.org/10.24815/ajse.v5i2.31668>

Sabilah, I., & Siswono, T. Y. E. (2018, November). Student's strategic competence toward open-ended problems before and after the transition to junior high school. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1108, No. 1, p. 012017). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1108/1/012017>

Sabiote, C., Olmedo-Romero, E.M., Expósito-López, J. (2022). The effects of teamwork on critical thinking: A serial mediation analysis of the influence of work skills and educational motivation in secondary school students. *Thinking Skills and Creativity* Volume 45. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1871187122000669>

Sagone, E., De Caroli, M.E., Falanga, R., & Indiana, M.L. (2020) Resilience and perceived self-efficacy in life skills from early to late adolescence. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 25(1), 882-890. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673843.2020.1771599>

Saraswathy, R. (2021). The Relationship Between Characteristics Of Creative Thinking In Mathematics And Writing To Learn Mathematics Among Ix Standard Students. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(14), 4203–4211. Retrieved from <https://www.turcomat.org/index.php/turkbilmate/article/view/11210>

Sarchami, R., Rajaei, S., & Aalaei, S. (2020). Evaluation of the relationship between religious beliefs and academic achievements of dental students. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 9(1), 305. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_576_19

Sari, DM., Ikhsan, M., & Abidin, Z. (2018). The development of learning instruments using the creative problem-solving learning model to improve students' creative thinking skills in mathematics. *Journal of Physics: Conf. Series* 1088 (2018) 012018. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1088/1/012018>

Schulz, A. (2023). Assessing student teachers' procedural fluency and strategic competence in operating and mathematizing with natural and rational numbers. *J Math Teacher Educ* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10857-023-09590-7>

Sebsibe, A. (2019). Overcoming Difficulties in Learning Calculus Concepts: The Case of Grade 12 Students. Unisa Institutional Repository. https://uir.unisa.ac.za/bitstream/handle/10500/26225/thesis_sebsibe_as.pdf?isAllowed=y&sequence=1&fbclid

Seetee, N., Chi, C., Dhir, A., & Chen, S. (2021). Validation of the science, mathematics, and English task value scales based on longitudinal data. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 19, 443-460. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-020-10081-x>

Serin, H. (2018). The use of extrinsic and intrinsic motivations to enhance student achievement in educational settings. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 5(1), 191-194. <https://doi.org/10.23918/ijsses.v5i1p191>

Setiawan, E.P.A., Setiawan, E.P.A., Siswono, T.Y.E., & Ekawati, R. (2018). Implementation of problem posing learning on conceptual understanding and adaptive reasoning. <https://doi.org/10.2991/icei-18.2018.104>

Silalahi, M., Inrawan, A., Putri, J. A., Indajang, K., & Sudirman, A. (2023). Increasing Motivation and Teamwork to Encourage Services for Posyandu Cadres in the City of Pematang Siantar. *Jurnal Pengabdian Nasional (JPN) Indonesia*, 4(1), 196-203. <https://doi.org/10.35870/jpni.v4i1.144>

Silalahi, R. M. (2019). Understanding Vygotsky's zone of proximal development for learning. *Polyglot: Jurnal Ilmiah*, 15(2), 169-186. <https://doi.org/10.19166/pji.v15i2.1544>

Singh, M. (2022). Role Of Analytical Thinking In Mathematics. <https://numberdyslexia.com/math-and-analytical-thinking-skills/>

So, I. (1964). Cognitive development in children: Piaget development and learning. *Journal, of Research in Science Teaching*, 2, 176-186. <https://cornerstone.lib.mnsu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1138&context=all>

Spaska, A. M., Savishchenko, V. M., Komar, O. A., & Maidanyk, O. V. (2021). Enhancing Analytical Thinking in Tertiary Students Using Debates. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 10(2), 879-889. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.10.2.879>

Stanford, J. (2022). The Development of Adaptive Reasoning in the Mathematics Classroom. *Learning to Teach Language Arts, Mathematics, Science, and Social Studies Through Research and Practice* 11(1). <https://openjournals.utoledo.edu/index.php/learningtoteach/article/view/580>

Stanton, A., & Stanton, W. (2015). Problem Solving, Critical Thinking, and Analytical Reasoning Skills Sought by Employers. <https://www.radford.edu/content/cobe/innovation-analytics/analytics/career-prep/report-e.html>

Stanton, W., & Perkins, V. (2015). Problem Solving, Critical Thinking, and Analytical Reasoning Skills Sought by Employers. Radford University. <https://www.radford.edu/content/cobe/innovation-analytics/analytics/career-prep/report-e.html>.

- Sugandi, A. I., & Bernard, M. (2020). Application of geogebra software to improve problem-solving skills in analytic geometry in prospective teachers students. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1657, No. 1, p. 012077). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1/012077>
- Sugandi, A. I., Bernard, M., & Linda, L. (2020). The effectiveness of geogebra-assisted problem-based online learning on mathematical reasoning skills in the covid-19 era. *AXIOMS: Journal of Mathematics Education Study Program*, 9(4), 993-1004. <https://doi.org/10.24127/AJPM.V9I4.3133>
- Sulaiman, M., Mat, Z., Husain, F. C., Sulaiman, A., Nizah, M. A. M., & Latiff, L. A. (2017). The impact of teamwork skills on students in Malaysian Public Universities. *The Social Sciences*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/306229244_The_Impact_of_Teamwork_skills_on_Students_in_Malaysian_Public_Universities
- Suryadi, D. (2019). *Landasan Filosofis Penelitian Desain Didaktis (DDR)*. Gapura Press. Bandung. https://opac.ikipgripta.ac.id/index.php?p=show_detail&id=7272
- Susilawati, W., Rachmawati, T.K., & Nuraida, I. (2021). Adaptive Reasoning Based on Microsoft Mathematics. *JTAM (Jurnal Teori dan Aplikasi Matematika)* 5(1):216. <https://doi.org/10.31764/jtam.v5i1.3918>
- Sya'Roni, A. R., Inawati, P. A., Guswanto, E., Susanto, & Hobri. (2020). Students' creative thinking skill in the flipped classroom blended learning of mathematics based on lesson study for learning community. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1563(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1563/1/012046>
- Thaneerananon, T., Triampo, W., & Nokkaew, A. (2019). Development of a Test to Evaluate Students' Analytical Thinking Based on Fact versus Opinion Differentiation. *International Journal of Instruction*, 9(2), 123-138. <https://doi.org/10.12973/iji.2016.929a>
- Thomas, M.S. Crosby, S., & Vanderhaar, J., (2019). Trauma-Informed Practices in Schools Across Two Decades: An Interdisciplinary Review of Research. *Review of Research in Education* 43(1):422-452. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333302379_Trauma-Informed_Practices_in_Schools_Across_Two_Decades_An_Interdisciplinary_Review_of_Research
- Tian, M., Yan, S., & Ning, W. (2018). Evaluating the effectiveness of snyder's theory-based group hope therapy to improve self-efficacy of university students in finance. *Neuroquantology*, 16(6). <https://doi.org/10.14704/nq.2018.16.6.1314>
- Topalov, J. P., & Radić-Bojanić, B. B. (2019). TEACHER TALK IN A YOUNG LEARNERS' ENGLISH CLASSROOM. *TEME*, 069-089. <https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=771779>
- Topalov, J., & Radić-Bojanić, B. (2013). Academic research skills of university students. *Romanian Journal of English Studies*, 10(1), 145-152. <https://doi.org/10.2478/rjes-2013-0012>
- Tsalaporta, E. (2021). Emotional Intelligence for sustainable engineering education: Incorporating soft skills in the capstone chemical engineering capstone design project. In *Proceedings of the 10th Engineering Education for Sustainable Development Conference, Cork, Ireland, 14-16 June 2021*; pp. 1-8. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/347434742_Emotional_Intelligence_for_sustainable_engineering_education_incorporating_soft_skills_in_the_capstone_chemical_engineering_capstone_design_project
- Tsao, J. Y., Ting, C. L., & Johnson, C. M. (2019). Creative outcome as implausible utility. *Review of General Psychology*, 23(3), 279-292. <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7102/11/10/621#B9-education-11-00621>
- Tuazon, A., & Torres, A. (2022). Predicting Academic Performance based on Students' Mathematics Motivation. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)* 13(2):402-409. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359686793_Predicting_Academic_Performance_based_on_Students%27_Mathematics_Motivation
- Van Rooy, D. L., & Viswesvaran, C. (2004). Emotional intelligence: A meta-analytic investigation of predictive validity and nomological net. *Journal of vocational Behavior*, 65(1), 71-95. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0001-8791\(03\)00076-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0001-8791(03)00076-9)
- Veerasamy, A. K., D'Souza, D., Lindén, R., & Laakso, M. J. (2019). Relationship between perceived problem-solving skills and academic performance of novice learners in introductory programming courses. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 35(2), 246-255. https://www.utupub.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/167074/Main%20document_revised_August%2031_2018.pdf?sequence=1
- Verschafel, L., Schukajlow, S., Star, J., & van Dooren, W. (). Word problems in mathematics education: a survey. *ZDM: the international journal on mathematics education* 52(1):1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-020-01130-4>
- Von der Embse, N., Jester, D., Roy, D., & Post, J. (2018). Test anxiety effects, predictors, and correlates: A 30-year meta-analytic review. *Journal of affective disorders*, 227, 483-493. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2017.11.048>
- Vu, Q. C., Pham, D. T. T., & Le, D. C. (2022). Correlations among perception, emotion and behavior in sustainable development of

mathematical creativity competency of primary school students in Vietnam. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 12(1), 282–296. <https://doi.org/10.36941/jesr-2022-0023>

Wahono, B., Chang, C. Y., & Retnowati, A. (2020). Exploring a direct relationship between students' problem-solving abilities and academic achievement: A STEM education at a coffee plantation area. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 17(2), 211-224. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1264688#:~:text=The%20results%20indicated%20that%20there%20was%20a%20positive,have%2C%>

Wahono, B., Chang, C. Y., & Retnowati, A. (2020). Exploring a direct relationship between students' problem-solving abilities and academic achievement: A STEM education at a coffee plantation area. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 17(2), 211-224. <https://doi.org/10.36681/tused.2020.22>

Wahyuni, S., Dahlan, J.A., & Juandi, D. (2021). Students' Mathematics Problem Solving Ability Through Model Eliciting Activities (MEAS). *Journal of Physics: Conference Series; Bristol Vol. 1882*. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1882/1/012079>

Wang, Q., Lee, K. C. S., & Hoque, K. E. (2020). The effect of classroom climate on academic motivation mediated by academic self-efficacy in a higher education institute in China. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 19(8), 194-213. <https://ijlter.net/index.php/ijlter/article/view/269>

Wati, I., Zaenuri., Dwijanto, D., Mulyono., Budi Waluya, S. & Rochmad. (2021). Conceptual understanding and productive disposition in trigonometry through generative learning. *Journal of Physics Conference Series* 1918(4):042050. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1918/4/042050>

Weidinger, A. F., Spinath, B., & Steinmayr, R. (2020). The value of valuing math: Longitudinal links between students' intrinsic, attainment, and utility values and grades in math. *Motivation Science*, 6(4), 413. <https://doi.org/10.1037/mot0000179>

Welch, C., Carbajal, M., Kumar, S., & Thammasitboon, S. (2020). Development and validation of a theory-informed group learning environment assessment tool for graduate medical education programs. *Journal of Graduate Medical Education*, 12(4), 447-454. <https://doi.org/10.4300/jgme-d-19-00748.1>

Wigfield, A. (1994). Expectancy-value theory of achievement motivation: A developmental perspective. *Educational psychology review*, 6, 49-78. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23359359#:~:text=Atkinson%20%281957%29%20originally%20defined%20>

Wigfield, A., & Eccles, J. S. (2020). 35 years of research on students' subjective task values and motivation: A look back and a look forward. In A. J. Elliot (Ed.), *Advances in motivation science* (pp. 161–198). Elsevier Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.adms.2019.05.002>

Wimmer, S., Lackner, H. K., Papousek, I., & Paechter, M. (2018). Goal orientations and activation of approach versus avoidance motivation while awaiting an achievement situation in the laboratory. *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, 1552. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01552>

Wulandari N. P., Rizky N. D., Antara P. A. (2020). Pendekatan Pendidikan Matematika Realistik Berbasis Open Ended Terhadap Kemampuan Pemecahan Masalah Matematika Siswa. *Jurnal Ilmiah Sekolah Dasar* 4, 131–142. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jisd.v4i2.25103>

Yahaya, A.; Bachok, N.S.E.; Yahaya, N.; Boon, Y.; Hashim, S.; Goh, M.L (2012). The impact of emotional intelligence element on academic achievement. *Arch. Des Sci.*; 2012; 65, pp. 2-17.

Yanti, A.W., Sutini., & Kurohman, T. (2020). Adaptive reasoning profile of students in solving mathematical problems viewed from field-dependent and field-independent cognitive style. *AIP Conference Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0000699>

Yarin, A. J., Encalada, I. A., Elias, J. W., Surichaqui, A. A., Sulca, R. E., & Pozo, F. (2022). Relationship between Motivation and Academic Performance in Peruvian Undergraduate Students in the Subject Mathematics. *Education Research International*, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/3667076>

You, J. W. (2018). Testing the three-way interaction effect of academic stress, academic self-efficacy, and task value on persistence in learning among Korean college students. *Higher Education*, 76(5), 921-935. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-018-0255-0>

Yurt, E. (2022). Mathematics self-efficacy as a mediator between task value and math anxiety in secondary school students. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction* 14(2) 1204-1221. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358954696_Mathematics_selfefficacy_as_a_mediator_between_task_value_and_math_anxiety_in_secondary_school_students

Yurtseven, R., Baysal, A., & Ocak, G. (2021). Analysis of the relationship between decision making skills and problem-solving skills of primary school students. *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching (IOJET)*, 8(3). 2117-2130. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1308060.pdf>

Zacccone, M. C., & Pedrini, M. (2019). The effects of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on students learning effectiveness. *Exploring*

the moderating role of gender. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 33(6), 1381-1394. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-03-2019-0099>

Zakariya, Y. (2022). Improving students' mathematics self-efficacy: A systematic review of intervention studies. *Frontiers Psychology Sec. Educational Psychology Volume 13 - 2022*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.986622>

Zakariya, Y. F., & Massimiliano, B. (2021). Development of mathematics motivation scale: A preliminary exploratory study with a focus on secondary school students. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1286333.pdf>

Zeidner, M. (2007). Test anxiety in educational contexts: Concepts, findings, and future directions. In *Emotion in education*, Eds. Paul A. Schutz & Reinhard Pekrun, CA: Academic Press, p. 165-184. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2007-04736-010>

Zhang, J., Bohrnstedt, G., Park, B. J., Ikoma, S., Ogut, B., & Broer, M. (2021). Mathematics Motivation and Its Relationship with Mathematics Performance: Evidence from the National Assessment for Educational Progress-High School Longitudinal Study of 2019 Overlap Sample. AIR-NAEP Working Paper 2021-03. American Institutes for Research. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED616670>

Zhoc, K.C.; Chung, T.S.; King, R.B. Emotional intelligence (EI) and self-directed learning: Examining their relation and contribution to better student learning outcomes in higher education. *Br. Educ. Res. J.* 2018, 44, 982–1004.

Ziegelbauer, C. and D'Errico, B. (2021). Eportfolio in teacher education and academic further education. *Irish Journal of Technology Enhanced Learning*, 6(1), 213-225. <https://doi.org/10.22554/ijtel.v6i1.78>

Zulfah., Astuti., Surya, YF., Marta, R., & Wijaya, TT. (2020). Measurement of mathematics problems solving ability using problem-based mathematics question. *Ahmad Dahlan International Conference on Mathematics and Mathematics Education Journal of Physics: Conference Series 1613 (2020) 012026*. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1613/1/012026>

Zwart, D. P., Noroozi, O., Van Luit, J. E., Goei, S. L., & Nieuwenhuis, A. (2020). Effects of Digital Learning Materials on nursing students' mathematics learning, self-efficacy, and task value in vocational education. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 44, 102755. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2020.102755>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Charmine F. Hormillada

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Jobell B. Jajalla, PhD

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines